

WHAT IS THE IMPACT OF DISTRIBUTED AGILE SOFTWARE
DEVELOPMENT ON TEAM PERFORMANCE?

MASTER THESIS

SUBMITTED FOR THE DEGREE

MASTER IN ENTERPRISE IT ARCHITECTURE (2018–2020)

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AT THE

ANTWERP MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

JUNE 2020

Abstract

Agile methodology has played a vital role in recent days for software development by overcoming the drawbacks of other popular SDLC (Software Development Life Cycle) models like Waterfall, Iterative and Spiral, etc. The Agile methodology was initially developed for small co-located teams, by being flexible and responding quickly to the customer requirements. This success story was also observed in several reports like Standish Group Chaos Report 2020.

Following this trend, agile practices had also caught interest in larger organizations, as well as to large-scale software development projects. However, there still seemed to be some challenges in incorporating and practicing Agile to explore benefits as it was defined in the Agile Manifesto in 2001. It was also very well observed in the Standish Group 2020 Chaos Report, which mentioned that big organizations were not as successful in practicing Agile for larger projects as compared to smaller projects (19% success in large size projects vs 59% success in small size projects). On the other hand, another survey done by Scott Ambler + Associates mentioned that the success ratio of the co-located agile team was higher than a distributed agile team. Despite such variation in success ratio, organizations still intended to do huge investment in implementing distributed agile software development model, was surprising and exploratory.

In this master thesis, I have tried to evaluate and explore all factors and characteristics associated with distributed agile software development with the help of the literature and thereafter, intended to find an answer about the impact of distributed agile software development on team performance. This was done by conducting a case study within Rabobank Payment domain, where, at one end I used maturity assessment model to derive the current maturity of the Rabobank Payment domain, and on other hand, the maturity score also helped to identify the gaps when a single model is used for evaluation. As my research aimed to identify the team performance of a distributed agile software development team, I used data statistics to do a comparison of the co-located agile team and distributed agile team within Rabobank Payment domain to derive to the conclusion.

The outcome of my research did find a direct co-relation between distributed agile software development and team performance but in addition to this, it also unboxed various factors attributing to the usage of maturity models and challenges within the distributed agile model which might have been given less importance by organization thus negatively impacting team performance.

Keywords: Agile methodology, distributed agile software development, team performance, assessment maturity models, data statistics.

Preface

This master thesis was written as part of the MEITA 2018-2020 (Executive Master in Enterprise IT Architecture) program at Antwerp Management School (AMS).

My specialization has been in Information technology as application/solution architect in various domains, within the Banking and Financial sector and due to the nature of this program, which was very much aligned to my career, it had caught my interest. Also, as I had always been associated with a consultancy organization that worked in a distributed model, initially with the waterfall model in lately with the agile model, the importance of performance has always been the key to success. This has also been a relevant topic with all sorts of the organization where time and material (resources) are the base of budgeting. Therefore, I chose to research the impact of distributed agile software development on team performance as the co-relation between distributed agile software development model and team performance has not got enough attention in the literature.

I would like to thank my promoter Dr. Yuri Bobbert for his support and guidance which helped me to structure my master thesis. His knowledge of challenges in banking and finance was very beneficial. I would also like to thank Dr. Hans Mulder for guiding me as a mentor and showing faith in my work and thought behind this master thesis. His support whenever I needed any information and his guidance to ensure that I kept my scope limited helped me craft my thesis as I had conceptualized.

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Chapter 1
Introduction

1 Introduction

In section 1.1, I will focus on the motivation for doing the research on evaluating why Agile methodology doesn't work efficiently in large enterprises (like Rabobank) with the distributed model as compared to small or medium enterprises. In section 1.2, I will then focus on the problem area and define the research question that has been the foundation of this master thesis. In section 1.3, I will define the scope and limitation of this master thesis followed with section 1.4 describing the target audience with the final section 1.5 presenting the thesis outline.

1.1 Problem Area

Agile has become the fastest growing IT development methodology with the majority of organizations doing agile implementations as stated in Harvard Business Review [Agile at scale (2018)¹]. However, post-implementation of Agile, for example in Rabobank, the return on investments was not up to the desired mark which was visible in the velocity graph of several Rabobank Payment agile teams which had not shown any sort of growth in last 3 years, and besides, the completion ratio depicted via burn down chart was around 50-70% instead of 100%. Prima facie it looks like big organizations are not as successful in practicing Agile for larger projects as compared to smaller projects (19% success in large size projects vs 59% success in small size projects). My statement is also supported by the Standish Group 2015 Chaos Report² and 2020 under section Chaos resolution by Agile versus Waterfall.

Another observation was that Rabobank is using a geographically distributed delivery model which comes with a list of challenges [Paasivaara, M., Durasiewicz, S., & Lassenius, C. (2008)] for example, communication problems [Berczuk, S. (2007)], lack of close physical proximity [Agerfalk, P., & Fitzgerald, B. (2006)], lack of team cohesion [Ramesh, B., Cao, L., Mohan, K., & Xu, P. (2006)], lack of shared context and knowledge [Yap, M. (2005)], and unavailability of team members [Yap, M. (2005)]. Scott Ambler + Associates, in their 2014 survey³ found that 38% of teams were located geographically apart and had just shown a success rate of around 52% and failure rate of around 54%. On the contrary, the success ratio was as high as 60% for co-located teams working in an agile development model with failure rate of 25%. Despite such known challenges and statistics, organizations still tend to implement the distributed agile software development model by doing huge investment in coaching, training and setting a different infrastructural setup for better productivity yet, the issues/challenges seem to persist and can be observed in the retrospective session of agile teams were commonly addressed concerns for lower velocity were misunderstanding, miscommunications, unable to get support quickly, etc.

¹ See <https://hbr.org/2018/05/agile-at-scale>

² See https://www.standishgroup.com/sample_research_files/CHAOSReport2015-Final.pdf

³ See <http://www.ambyssoft.com/surveys/stateOfITUnion2014Q2.html>,
<http://www.ambyssoft.com/surveys/stateOfITUnion201209.html>

I also found weak guidelines in the agile manifesto and ambiguities within agile maturity models. At one end, where agile manifesto fails to give any direction based on the type of organizations or type of projects (small, medium, or large) and contradicts other agile methodologies. For example, principle 6 of agile manifesto illustrates the importance of face-face communication for working efficiently as an agile organization, thus challenging and contradicting the core principle of distributed agile methodology which promotes working at a different location to achieve the goal.

Another phenomenon was identified at Rabobank, where the Payments department worked on 4 different methodologies that are, waterfall, scrum, DevOps, and simplify@scale, within 4 years. Such frequent implementation impacts team retention as people tend to feel less motivated due to such frequent change in working culture and was seen within the Rabobank simplify@scale survey report which depicted lower associate satisfaction index and was conducted to get feedback from various agile teams after the implementation of simplify@scale agile methodology. It thus remains unclear on the need and objective for such experiments. Such trends of experimenting with agile methodology implementation within the organization involve huge IT investment, thus impacting the financial aspect of an organization and team performance as the team needs to get accustomed to the new methodology which requires time and effort.

Hence, I decided to explore the impact of distributed agile software development on team performance by analyzing the under mentioned problem statement.

“Distributed agile team lead to team performance problems and thereby causing a negative impact on software development.”

1.2 Research Question

My topic of research focuses on the problem statement, **“distributed agile team lead to team performance problems and thereby causing negative impact to software development.”**

My focus is to check the validity of my problem statement within the Rabobank Payment domain. To do the initial assessment, I did a preliminary interview with few delivery managers IT of Rabobank to get an opinion and direction on the master thesis, gather insights that can benefit the organization, and help me sharpen my research project. Thus, after getting a direction from management and doing a preliminary examination of existing research and literature, I decided to execute my research to address the defined problem statement. Thereby, this master thesis aims at answering the research question (MRQ):

“What is the impact of distributed agile software development on team performance?”

As team performance is a subjective entity, the impact will be done with the help of a hypothesis by comparing the team performance of co-located agile teams and distributed agile teams. This has been further explained in chapter 2.

The conceptual model is depicted in Figure 1.1 depicting the independent and the dependent variable

Independent variable	Dependent variable
Distributed Agile Software Development	Team Performance

Figure 1. 1: Conceptual Model

During my literature study when I scanned the library of the University of Antwerp UA and google scholar, I encountered 89 peer-reviewed journals which focused on distributed agile software development model and met the search criteria specific to my research. On the other hand, there were around 85 journals published as research papers on team performance. The literature strategy will be discussed further in detail in chapter 2 to illustrate the applied approach.

Scott Ambler + Associates, in their 2014 survey also found that 61% of agile teams are geographically distributed but have a return on investment scale at 3.2/10, quality at 4.4/10, delivery time at 2.6/10, stakeholder satisfaction at 4.8/10 and team morale at 4.8/10. These low figures do indicate a potential impact on team performance due to the distributed agile software model. Thus, I found my research very relevant for the organization working in a distributed agile software model as I intend to research exploring its correlation and their probable impact on team performance which might have a positive contribution to improving the figures as mentioned above.

Thus, based on the literature study, these variables are illustrated in subsequent sections.

1.2.1 Distributed Agile Software Development

A distributed software development (Woodward, E., Surdek, S., & Ganis, M., 2010) is defined as a group of members actively collaborating on a common software/ system separated by

- Distance
- Time zone
- Culture

The reasons for distributing your agile team will be different for each organization. They might include the availability of resources in different locations, closeness to certain clusters, proximity to customers, or cost advantages. Their primary goal is to build up worth goods at reduced prices than the co-located developments by enhancing resources.

1.2.2 Team Performance

Team performance [Lindsjörn, Y., Sjøberg, D. I., Dingsøy, T., Bergersen, G. R., & Dybå, T. (2016)] may be defined as the “extent to which a team can meet established quality, cost, and time objectives” [Hoegl and Gemuenden, (2001)].

By conducting this research with the outlined research question in mind, it should be possible to identify the impacts of a distributed agile team along with their associated characteristics and parameters on team performance.

1.3 Scope and limitations

As the master thesis is constrained by time, the scope of the project has also been adjusted to be able to produce results within the time restrictions. Due to this, the scope has been limited to the Rabobank Netherlands Payments domain.

This master thesis does not aim at introducing new theory regarding team performance and distributed agile software development rather, I intend to re-use the information present in existing literature like “Distributed Agile Development: A Survey of Challenges and Solutions [Harneet Kaur, Hisham M. Haddad (2015)]”, which, with the help of surveys had identified several challenges concerning distributed agile software development model. The same has also been cited in several other research papers/articles/journals. The main intention of re-using the information present in literature is to gain a deeper knowledge and insight into the research area and evaluate it against the Rabobank Payments domain. For this research, the factors of distributed agile software development associated with team performance are being considered and have been kept within scope. As there can be several other factors impacting team performance, those are not being considered for this master thesis.

The background theory about distributed agile software development methodology and its underlying principles are also included in this master thesis to give a broader overview and good insight into the topics that are essential for the analysis. They will not be elaborated endlessly but focus on giving a brief insight into what studies have been conducted and are recorded in literature.

1.4 Target audience

There are several who could have an interest in this research, but as this research is done as part of my master thesis for MEITA program, the target audiences for this research are the jury members who will be evaluating my research, my mentors and my colleagues who would have helped me in peer reviews and providing valuable feedback.

1.5 Report Outline

Table 1.1 consist of the overview of different chapters along with a summary about the chapters which will help in answering the main research question

Chapter 1 Introduction	This chapter includes motivation for conducting this research as well as the overall problem description and research question for the master thesis, scope, and intended audience.
Chapter 2 Research Methodology	This chapter will illustrate various steps associated with research methodology thus helping to answer the research question.
Chapter 3 Distributed Agile Software Development	This chapter includes background theories about the distributed agile software development methodology and its characteristics. This chapter will also describe a brief overview of the different software development methodologies practiced within Rabobank.
Chapter 4 Team Performance	This chapter includes background theories about team performance based on existing literature.
Chapter 5 Assessment of the Frameworks	This chapter includes the analysis of several assessment models/frameworks to do maturity assessment of agile teams and select the ones which can be used for this research.
Chapter 6 Research Analysis	This chapter will explore the problem area and execute the research method to get the answer associated with the main research question (MRQ). In addition to the research execution and analysis, it will also state the limitations while performing the research and thereafter will draw a conclusion based on data analysis.
Chapter 7 Conclusions, Recommendations and Further Research	This chapter will include the conclusion for entire research based on the findings from previous chapters along with recommendations to the target audience. In addition to the conclusion and recommendation, this chapter will also include suggestions for further research.
REFLECTION	This section will depict the journey in brief and will enlist what could have been done differently if I was to do research again.

Table 1. 1: Report outline

Chapter 2

Research Methodology

2 Research Approach

My research falls under category applied research as I intend to explore the impact of the distributed agile software development on team performance and gain a deeper understanding of the topic. The first choice of conducting this applied research was by using the design science research method. The goal of design science is to deliver an artifact as a practical contribution to science [Peppers, Tuunanen, Rothenberger, & Chatterjee, (2008)]. However, it was not very clear what the impact of distributed agile software development has on team performance, hence the idea of an artifact creation [Hevner, 2004] was very unlikely to be realized due to time limitations. Thus, the choice of using the design science research method was not appropriate for this research. The choice is made to use a qualitative research method and to perform an exploratory case study, where the co-relation of distributed agile software development and team performance is explored [Recker, (2013)].

With the help of a literature study, the features and characteristics associated with distributed agile software development methodology are enlisted along with the factors, that collectively define team performance [Dingsoyr, T., Faegri, T. E., Dyba, T., Haugset, B., & Lindsjorn, Y. (2016)]. In the sequel to this, the research gives insights about the possible impacts of distributed agile software development on team performance thereby evaluating the outcome by testing the results across Rabobank payment domain teams.

A set of predefined questionnaires from existing assessment models is shortlisted based on a detailed analysis of 87 assessment models and frameworks. This assessment has been carried out with the inputs from agile coaches of the Rabobank payment domain, understanding the organizational culture and its way of working. This set of questionnaire helps in assessing the team performance and thereby understanding the impact of distributed agile framework features on the team performance parameters. The results have also been cross-validated with the agile team as well as with the management of the Rabobank Payment domain to draft the conclusion of this research.

Using this approach, two different analysis on the same case is performed, framing this research further to an embedded single-case study. Exploratory case study research is shaped as seen in figure 2.1.

Figure 2. 1: Exploratory case study [Recker, (2013)]

First, a plan is drafted to approach this research. Thereafter the design phase focuses on doing the literature research and extracting information needed to conduct the case study. As part of the preparation phase, questionnaires for conducting interviews with expert panels are selected. The experts are given all necessary background about the objective of research and sufficient time to provide their answers. The questionnaires for agile teams are also prepared and circulated to get their set of answers necessary for answering the research question. The results are then collected and analyzed to evaluate the validity of the research question and provide the necessary recommendations to post the analysis. In the case of the validity of the research question, the necessary recommendations will be also shared with Rabobank stakeholders. This sharing phase is not an explicit part of this research as it depends on the outcome of the result.

This will further be discussed in depth in the subsequent section within this chapter.

2.1 Literature strategy

The literature strategy is based on two variables of this research: distributed agile software development and team performance. The literature study has been set up based on Systematic Literature Review (SLR) which, according to Shahin, Babar, and Zhu (2017), is the most used research method in “Evidence-Based Software Engineering”. According to the researchers, SLR aims to provide a well-defined process for identifying, evaluating, and interpreting all available data that is relevant to a specific research question or topic.

To answer the main research question, relevant peer-reviewed publications were searched for. I also searched for relevant literature to scientifically substantiate the introduction and problem definition in the preliminary research where possible. During the literature search, systematic search has been mainly used by searching search engines based on combined search terms and the snowball method by searching articles that were used as a reference in the articles found.

Because most publications and the terms themselves are in English, the search has been mainly done with English search terms. EndNote is used to sort and categorize the articles found. To reduce the search results found to a manageable selection, the search process in figure 2.2 below has been followed [Budgen, D., Burn, A. J., Brereton, O. P., Kitchenham, B. A., & Pretorius, R. (2010)].

Figure 2. 2: Stages of Systematic Literature review

Phase 1: In this phase, the aim is to find a comprehensive and unbiased collection of primary studies from the literature related to the research questions. For the electronic search, I leveraged the major databases that are widely used software engineering (SE) research such as the University of Antwerp (UA) Library⁴ and Google scholar⁵. These are rich and comprehensive databases containing bibliographic information about my research variable, distributed agile software development, and team performance. I also observed that the IEEE Explore Digital Library⁶ is also a large database of scientific studies. However, due to its premium subscription, I chose to use it for extracting the valid research articles based on my search query and extract the actual research with the help of google scholar or UA library.

Our search terms stem from the research questions and can be categorized into 2 dimensions, as shown in Table 2.1. On the one hand, I aim to explore the two research variables as part of 2 dimensions i.e. distributed agile software development and team performance considered for the primary studies. On the other hand, I aim to discover existing techniques/assessment models/frameworks to test these research variables. I would be making use of benlinders⁷ who had consolidated more than 80 of such assessment models/frameworks and guidelines.

To ensure a sufficient scope of searching, certain search techniques have been used such as;

- Boolean logic for combined search or exclusion with AND, OR, NOT
- Exact phrase, to enable searching by exact word combination
- Field-specific, search by title and/or summary

⁴ See <https://www.uantwerpen.be>

⁵ See <https://scholar.google.com>

⁶ See <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org>

⁷ See www.benlinders.com

Dimension	Search Keywords
Distributed agile software development	“distributed agile software development”, timeline 2001 onwards, Peer-Reviewed, agile software development, distributed software development, agile development, software development, scrum, agile
Team performance	“team performance”, timeline 2001 onwards, team performance, computer software development, agile software development, “team performance in software development”

Table 2. 1: Literature Search Dimensions and Keywords

Phase 2: In this phase, the aim is to implement inclusion and exclusion criteria to identify the suitability of primary studies and making decisions for inclusion or exclusion of an article in the SLR based on the addressed research questions. Our inclusion and exclusion criteria are shown in Table 2.2.

Type	Description
Inclusion	Articles are associated with Agile methodology within software engineering
	Articles are associated with the distributed software development model
	The study comes from an acceptable source such as a peer-reviewed scientific journal, conference, and symposium
	The study describes solid evidence by using rigorous analysis, experiments, case studies, experience reports, surveys, field studies, and simulation
	Articles are in English
Exclusion	The study did not undergo a peer-review process
	Articles are associated with the non-IT domain
	Articles are not in English
	The study is a shorter version of another study which appeared in a different source

Table 2. 2: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

In this phase, the aim is also to check the references of the filtered literature selected as an outcome of phase 2 and reassess them and let it undergo inclusion and exclusion criteria implementation and identify the suitable literature for this research.

Phase 3: In this phase, all the selected non-duplicate articles as an outcome of phase 2 are analyzed and synthesized such that, they are suitable and sufficient for answering the main research question.

For executing phase 2 and phase 3, the quality assessment criteria are being used to determine the rigorousness and credibility of the used research methods and the relevance of the studies. This assessment is important to limit bias in conducting this SLR, to obtain insight into potential differences, and to support the interpretation of the results. Three main quality assessment criteria have been applied that is based on the assessment criteria introduced in [Kitchenham, B., Pearl Brereton, O., Budgen, D., Turner, M., Bailey, J., & Linkman, S. (2009)].

The 3 quality assessment criteria are:

- **Relevance:** As part of this assessment criteria, the focus is to accumulate only those studies which have enough information to answer the research question. This quality assessment has been done according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- **Coverage:** As part of this assessment criteria, all the selected articles are reviewed in iterations so that no relevant studies are missed. To achieve that, a search is performed on the entire list of relevant studies following the screening of the titles, abstracts, keywords, and conclusion. Moreover, a snowballing process is conducted to broaden the scope of selected studies
- **Validation:** As part of this assessment criteria, an analysis of the searched studies is done and checked if the primary studies contain the necessary information to answer the main research question.

The result of this systematic literature review will be illustrated in subsequent chapters i.e. chapter 3 which will have the findings associated with distributed agile software development, chapter 4 which will describe the findings associated with team performance.

2.2 Theoretical Model

The theoretical model depicted in figure 2.3 illustrates the research question i.e. exploring the impacts of distributed agile software development on team performance.

Levels	Independent variable	Dependent variable	Measures
Multiple geographical location Cultural diversity Experience diversity	Distributed Agile Software Development	Team Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Low Velocity ✓ Inability to finish requirements in committed timeframe ✓ Lower IT retention ✓ Miscommunication and misunderstanding within team

Figure 2. 3: Theoretical model

2.3 Research Design

As described by [Robson, 1993], a case study is defined as a strategy of doing research which involves an empirical investigation of a particular contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context using multiple sources of evidence.

2.3.1 Case Study Research

To answer my research question, I decided to do an exploratory case study [Recker, (2013)] and applying my research on the Rabobank Payment domain. This research

design can help me gain further insight into the impacts of distributed agile software development on team performance.

The next step in the research design is to identify the type of case study design and its corresponding unit of analysis [Recker, (2013)] as depicted in figure 2.4.

Figure 2. 4: Case Study Design Recker (2013)

For this research a single-case, a holistic approach is most appropriate to design the case study. The choice of a single case has been taken since the execution of this case study is limited to the Rabobank payment domain. In addition to this, it will be interesting to see all variants within the domain concerning the distributed agile team. Thus, the choice of using a holistic approach has been selected to see if there is any impact of a distributed agile team on team performance by comparing various aspects while working in a distributed software development model.

2.3.2 Case study description

Rabobank⁸ is a Dutch multinational banking and financial services company headquartered in Utrecht, Netherlands. It is a global leader in food and agriculture financing and sustainability-oriented banking. With 9.5 million customers⁹ and operates in 40 countries with 43822 employees (FTE) and a net profit of 2203 million Euro, Rabobank is one of the leading Dutch banks.

⁸ See <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rabobank>

⁹ See <https://www.rabobank.com/en/images/annual-report-2019.pdf>

Due to such a vast distributed operating model, I found my research very relevant as I intend to research exploring their correlation and their probable impact on team performance within the organization like Rabobank Payment domain using case study exploratory research.

The scope of the case study focuses on the Rabobank Payment domain and its associated 12+ teams which operates in 2 geographical locations i.e. India and The Netherlands. Some agile teams within the domain have associates at both locations thus having cultural diversity within the team, whereas some only operate from the Netherlands with or without cultural diversity with its team. This case study research will thus help in understanding the team performance of these 12+ distributed agile teams and will help me validate my research question.

2.4 [Exploratory Research](#)

Exploratory Research is research conducted for a problem that has not been studied more clearly, establishes priorities, develops operational definitions, and improves the final research design (Shields & Rangarajan, 2013). In this case, I try to explore the correlation between distributed agile software development and team performance. For this research, in addition to literature, data is collected with the help of interviews with team management, questionnaires answered by agile team members, documentation, and observation of several agile teams (as an observer and also as a participant).

2.4.1 [Data Collection](#)

As Rabobank Payment domain teams are located in 2 geographic location, with the management team being located in the Netherlands and the agile teams distributed across 2 geographical location i.e. India and Netherlands, it was very convenient to have interviews with management located in the Netherlands and have the questionnaires answered with the help of online surveys. In addition to the two data collection techniques, as I have been part of the Rabobank Payment domain for several years, it was very easy for me to get data by observing my team and also other teams and getting it proven with the help of documentation associated with respective agile teams. Thus, I also chose observation and documentation as the other data collection techniques for my research.

[Interviews:](#)

The qualitative research interview for my research relied on purposive sampling, where the participants who were part of the interview process as well as for responding to online surveys were already working in the distributed agile software model and had in-depth and detailed information about the same. As the objective of this data collection technique is to define questions, propose new theory constructs, and/or build new theories [Recker, (2013)], I chose to use both unstructured and semi-structured exploratory interviews.

During the start of the research, unstructured interviews are planned with agile coaches and delivery managers IT to understand various aspects associated with distributed agile software development within Rabobank along with in-depth information around the topic like associated training, processes and practices proposed and followed within Rabobank Payment domain concerning working in a distributed agile software model. After the unstructured interviews, semi-structured interviews are planned with the management involving pre-defined questionnaires. These questionnaires will help to calculate the maturity assessment of the agile teams which in turn translates to the team performance as per the perception of the management.

In addition to conducting the interviews with management, data is collected with the help of online surveys which comprises questionnaires from existing agile assessment models. These questionnaires, which need to be answered by the agile team members help in understanding the facts associated with the maturity of the team from team's perception, processes, and practices followed by team and some vital information on how the distributed agile software model has been implemented within Rabobank payment domain. Table 2.3 depicts the information on the people involved in this data collection technique.

The output of these answers can help in understanding the gaps during the data analysis phase.

Role	Number of Interviewees
Agile Coach	1
Delivery Manager IT	2
Product Owner	3
Agile team member	23

Table 2. 3: Data Collection (Interviews)

Documentation and Observation:

The other data collection technique used in my research are documentation and observation. At one end where documentation help in getting the facts associated with team functioning as mentioned in Table 2.4.

Document type	Description
Burndown chart	It shows the ideal progress of a release or a sprint from start to finish compared with the actual daily progress
Velocity Graph	A velocity chart shows the sum of estimates of the work delivered across all iterations
Confluence Page	This Atlassian's content collaboration tool helps to know about various agile teams and their composition of team members. It also comprises of the overall hierarchy of team structure within the domain

JIRA Board	The board will depict apart from the user stories ¹⁰ , all the issues highlighted during retrospective are also enlisted which acted as a hurdle for the team.
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Table 2. 4: Data Collection (Documentation)

On the other hand, as I have been part of Rabobank, there were few observations which also clearly showed existing challenges within the distributed agile software development teams and was evident as an action item during the retrospective session within Jira Board and is enlisted in table 2.5 which mentions the observed parameters and the participants for the observation.

Observation	Participants
Miscommunication, misunderstanding	Agile team and individual
Team coordination	Agile Team
Openness during the retrospective session	Individual
Supporting each other	Individual
Accountability	Agile team
Constructive feedback	Individual

Table 2. 5: Data Collection (Observation)

Scoring:

In my research, the data collection method such as interviews, online surveys, documentation, and observation will be scored using Likert 2,3 and 5-point scale [Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S., & Pal, D. (2015)] to depict the maturity of the agile team. The overall score of individual participants will then be used in the data analysis phase and is illustrated in Appendix 2. Chapter 6 will elaborate on this in detail.

2.4.2 Data Analysis

As my research is qualitative, data collection and data analysis are interwoven or even dependant on each other [Recker, (2013)]. I will thus be testing my research question with the help of existing agile assessment models¹¹.

For the selection of the assessment model used for testing, I will be using a coding technique to categorize evaluated assessment models into frameworks, guideline and assessment tools, thereafter mapping the results with Rabobank culture and way of working and selecting the frameworks suitable for Rabobank, thus helping me to deduce my research question. Chapter 5 will elaborate this further in detail.

After the selection of the assessment, frameworks have been made to test the research question, I will be executing the test with the help of data collected from literature, interviews, questionnaires, documentation, and observation to validate my research question. The results will then be mapped using a case research matrix as mentioned in table 2.6. Chapter 6 will elaborate this further in detail.

¹⁰ See <https://www.scrum.org/index.php/resources/scrum-guide>

¹¹ See www.benlinders.com

Theory	Observation
Mentioned	Identified
Mentioned	Non-Identified
Not Mentioned	Identified

Table 2. 6: Case Research Matrix

As my research question focuses on the impact of distributed agile software development on team performance, which can be analyzed efficiently using statistical methods [Eisele, P. (2015)]. Thus, for my research, the data analysis will include both descriptive statistics [Spriestersbach, A., Röhrig, B., Prel, J. D., Gerhold-Ay, A., & Blettner, M. (2009)] and inferential statistics [Vieira, E. T. (2017)]. At one end, where descriptive statistics will be used to calculate the maturity of Rabobank payment domain along with individual maturity of co-located agile teams and distributed agile teams, inferential statistics will be used to answer the MRQ with the help of a hypothesis by comparing the team performance of co-located agile teams and distributed agile teams.

Descriptive statistics:

Descriptive statistics [Spriestersbach, A., Röhrig, B., Prel, J. D., Gerhold-Ay, A., & Blettner, M. (2009)] are brief descriptive coefficients that summarize a given data set, which can be either a representation of the entire or a sample of a population. Descriptive statistics are broken down into measures of central tendency and measures of variability (spread). Measures of central tendency include the mean, median, and mode, while measures of variability include the standard deviation¹², variance¹³, the minimum, and maximum variables, and the kurtosis¹⁴ and skewness¹⁵.

Inferential statistics:

Inferential statistics [Vieira, E. T. (2017)] are often used to compare the differences between the treatment groups. Inferential statistics use measurements from the sample of subjects in the experiment to compare the treatment groups and make generalizations about the larger population of subjects. In inferential statistics, data are analyzed from a sample to make inferences in the larger collection of the population. The purpose is to answer or test the hypotheses. A hypothesis (plural hypotheses) is a proposed explanation for a phenomenon. Hypothesis tests are thus procedures for making rational decisions about the reality of observed effects.

In inferential statistics, the term 'null hypothesis' (H₀ 'H-naught,' 'H-null') denotes that there is no relationship (difference) between the population variables in question [Travers, J. C., Cook, B. G., & Cook, L. (2017)]. The alternative hypothesis (H₁ and H_a) denotes that a statement between the variables is expected to be true [Travers, J. C., Cook, B. G., & Cook, L. (2017)].

¹² See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Standard_deviation

¹³ See <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Variance>

¹⁴ See <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kurtosis>

¹⁵ See <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Skewness>

As the data is collected using interviews, online questionnaires, documentation, and observation to validate my research question, the statistical test will involve 2 separate groups i.e. distributed agile software development team and co-located software development team. Based on the outcome of the data collection phase, a parametric or non-parametric test will have to be performed [Sedgwick, P. (2015)]. Table 2.7 depicts the various types of parametric and non-parametric tests. Based on the data evaluation which will be described in chapter 6, one of the tests from table 2.7 will be used to perform the inferential statistical test. Chapter 6 will illustrate this in detail.

Parametric Test	Non-Parametric Test
One Sample t-test	Sign Test, Wilcoxon's signed-rank test
Two-Sample Paired t-test,	Sign Test, Wilcoxon's signed-rank test
Two-Sample Unpaired t-test	Mann-Whitney U-test, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test
ANOVA test	Kruskal-Wallis test, Jonckheere test, Friedman test
Pearson correlation coefficient test	Spearman rank-order test

Table 2. 7: Parametric and Non-Parametric Test

2.4.3 Conclusion

After the data analysis, I will be concluding concerning the findings as an outcome of the data analysis phase. Chapters 6 and 7 will elaborate this further in detail.

Chapter 3

Distributed Agile Software Development

3 Software Development

The software development method (or in other words: the software development model or the software development life cycle) is a definition of an abstract process used for the development of software, including activities like requirement analysis, coding, testing, maintenance, etc. [Zima, D. (2015)]. Figure 3.1 depicts a representation of the basic software development model.

Figure 3. 1: Basic Software Development Model [Zima, D. (2015)]

There are various software development methods as mentioned within the Forrester report [West D, Grant T, Gerush M and D'Silva D (2010)]. These models are further categorized into two categories: Agile and Traditional and have been well described and compared in Annals of Software Engineering [Abrahamsson, P. (2002)].

Table 3.1 depicts the software development methods mentioned in Forrester's report [West D, Grant T, Gerush M, and D'Silva D (2010)] along with its categorization.

Software Development Methods	Categories
Adaptive Software Development	Agile
Agile Unified Process	Agile
Crystal Methods	Agile
Dynamic Systems Development Methodology	Agile
eXtreme Programming	Agile
Feature Driven Development	Agile
Kanban	Agile
Lean Software Development	Agile
Scrum	Agile
Rational Unified Process	Agile
Test-Driven Development	Agile
Behaviour Driven Development	Agile
Agile Data Method	Agile
Six Sigma	Traditional
Iterative Development	Traditional
Waterfall	Traditional
Spiral	Traditional

Table 3. 1: Software Development Methods

As my research focuses on identifying the impact of the independent variable i.e. distributed agile software development, it is important to understand the concept of agile software development first and thereafter the integration of distributed software development and agile software development. This chapter will focus on these aspects based on a literature study.

3.1 Agile Software Development

Agile manifesto¹⁶ defines Agile as a better way of developing software by doing it and helping others do it and emphasizes on below goals:

Individuals and interactions over processes and tools
Working software over comprehensive documentation
Customer collaboration over contract negotiation
Responding to change over following a plan.

Agile Software Development Methodologies and Practices [Williams, L. (2010)], states that the concept of agile was created and evolved in the mid-1990s. It emerged as an attempt to more formally and explicitly embrace higher rates of change in software requirements and customer expectations.

Agile encompasses various methodologies, including Adaptive Software Development (ASD) [Highsmith, J. (1997)], Agile Unified Process (AUP) [Ambler, S. (2006)], Crystal Methods [Cockburn, A. (2004)], Dynamic Systems Development Methodology (DSDM) [Tuffs, D., Stapleton, J., West, D. and Eason, Z. (1999)], eXtreme Programming (XP) [Anderson, A., Beattie, R., and Beck, K. (1998)], Feature Driven Development (FDD) [Coad, P., de Luca, J. and Lefebvre, E. (1999)], Kanban [Ladas, C. (2009)], Lean Software Development [Poppendieck, M. and Poppendieck, T. (2003)], Scrum [Schwaber, K. (1996)].

The agile methodology is based on the “iterative enhancement” [Basili, V.R. and Turner, A.J. (1975)] technique [Cohen, D., Lindvall, M. and Costa, P. (2004)]. As an iteration-based methodology, each iteration in the agile methodology represents a small scale and self-contained Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) by itself [Williams, L. (2010)]. Unlike the Spiral model [Boehm, B. (1986)], agile methods assume simplicity in all practices [Cohen, D., Lindvall, M. and Costa, P. (2004)].

Figure 3.2 depicts a representation of the agile software development process [Lyoko, G., Phiri, J., & Phiri, A. (2016)] and comprises of all phases of the same.

Figure 3. 2: Agile Software Development [Lyoko, G., Phiri, J., & Phiri, A. (2016)]

¹⁶ See <https://agilemanifesto.org/>

As agile encompasses various methodologies, also mentioned in table 3.1, the Rabobank Payment domain uses scrum methodology [Schwaber, K. (1996)] for implementing the agile practices within its teams.

3.1.1 Scrum Methodology

Forbes [Forbes Technology Council. (2016)] defines Scrum as “Scrum is a flexible and collaborative way to manage a software project. It’s a framework that lets you move quickly and pivot easily when needed”.

Scrum guide¹⁷ defines scrum as a framework within which, people can address complex adaptive problems, while productively and creatively delivering products of the highest possible value.

Scrum is:

- Lightweight
- Simple to understand
- Difficult to master

Scrum is a process framework that has been used to manage work on complex products since the early 1990s. Scrum is not a process, technique, or definitive method. Rather, it is a framework within which one can employ various processes and techniques. Scrum makes clear the relative efficacy of the product management and work techniques so that one can continuously improve the product, the team, and the working environment.

Figure 3.3 depicts a representation of the general idea of the scrum process dynamics [Cohn (2008)].

Figure 3. 3: General idea of the scrum process dynamics [Cohn (2008)]

¹⁷ See <https://www.scrumguides.org/docs/scrumguide/v2017/2017-Scrum-Guide-US.pdf>

As my thesis doesn't aim to focus in-depth on the scrum methodology, I have thus, only mentioned an overview of agile scrum methodology, as its being used within the Rabobank organization, without mentioning the processes and practices of the methodology.

3.1.2 Success Factor with Agile Software Development

The Critical Success Factor (CSF) approach for identifying and measuring an organization's performance was first developed by [Rockart (1979)] and later on refined and became well- established [Chow, T., Cao, D., (1981)]. CSF is defined by [Bullen and Rockart (1981)] as "the limited number of areas in which satisfactory results will ensure successful competitive performance for the individual, department, or organization."

Table 3.2 depicts the list of all the success factors for agile software development along with its classification into 5 dimensions; organizational, process, project, people, and technical [RamadanDarwish, N., & M. Rizk, N. (2015)].

Dimension	Main Success Factors	Sub Success Factors
Organizational	Corporate Culture	Support from top management
		Team Environment
People	User Involvement	Handling commercial pressures
		Stakeholder politics
	Team Capability	Effective project management skills
		Ability to handle the project's complexity
		Decision time
		Effective communication and feedback
Process	Project Management Process	The minimum change in requirement
		Simplicity in process
		Good reporting of project status
	Project Definition Process	Risk management
		Time allocation
		Accurate estimates of project resources
Active Testing	Code review	
Project	Clear Objectives and Goals	Project type
		Project nature
	Realistic schedule	
	Realistic budget	Team distribution
		Team size
Clear Requirements and Specifications		
Technical	Selecting the Proper Agile Method	Configuring the necessary tools and infrastructure
	Using Advanced Technology	Familiarity with technology

Table 3. 2: Success factor for Agile Software Development

Hypothesis 3.1: *It can thus be concluded that to have success in agile software development, the success factors associated with the 5 dimensions must then be addressed by the agile teams, and the management.*

3.2 Distributed Software Development

A distributed software development or global software development (GSD) [Woodward, E., Surdek, S., & Ganis, M. (2010), Stadler, M., Vallon, R., Pazderka, M., & Grechenig, T. (2019)] comprises of software development teams, whose team members are sited in different, geographically dispersed, locations. Next to geographical separation, there are also cultural, temporal, and configurational dimensions to consider.

Geographical Distance can be measured directionally and is described as “the effort required for one actor to visit another at the latter's home site” [Ågerfalk, P. J., Fitzgerald, B., Holmström Olsson, H., & Ó Conchúir, E. (2005)]. The Allen-Curve states that “the probability that people in a given organization will communicate with each other declines precipitously the farther away from each other they are situated and reaches an asymptotic level at about 50 meters”. This is not only valid for face-to-face communication, but the data from the study also shows a decline in the usage of all communication media with increasing distance [Allen, T. J., Henn, G. (2006)].

Socio-cultural Distance is one of the most complexes and therefore least understood dimensions of distance, but a critical element in a distributed setting [Casey, V. (2010)]. It involves national as well as organizational culture, work ethic, and motivation, as well as spoken languages. Two individuals with different national backgrounds may share a common organizational culture and therefore have a low socio-cultural distance. A low socio-cultural distance lowers risks and increases communication [Ågerfalk, P. J., Fitzgerald, B., Holmström Olsson, H., & Ó Conchúir, E. (2005)]. In the scope of the same company, sites still often differ in various aspects like informal habits, practices, or processes [Herbsleb, J. D. (2007)].

Configurational Dimension is defined by O'Leary and Cummings as “the arrangement of members across sites independent of the spatial and temporal distances among them [O'Leary, & Cummings. (2007)]. Especially situations with a concentrated core team and isolated members on different sites decrease awareness towards remote colleagues. A larger number of sites also boosts complexity for coordination and raises conflict potential [O'Leary, & Cummings. (2007)].

Temporal Distance, in terms of different time zones, impedes synchronous communication between individuals and therefore hurts communication [Carmel, E., & Agarwal, R. (2001)].

3.3 Distributed Agile Software Development

The pairing of distributed software development with agile software development is referred to as distributed agile software development [Paasivaara, M., Durasiewicz, S., & Lassenius, C. (2008)]. In terms of scope of this thesis (for Rabobank) the distributed agile software development is being carried out in multiple locations within The Netherlands and India thus limiting the geographical location to two continents.

The reasons for distributing your agile team will be different for each organization. They might include the availability of resources in different locations, closeness to certain clusters, proximity to customers, or cost advantages. Their primary goal is to build up worth goods at reduced prices than the co-located developments by enhancing resources.

Even though this model has a huge benefit in terms of project cost, (as the distributed model generally involves lesser cost as compared to co-location projects) and can leverage the emergence of large multi-skilled labor forces in lower-cost economies [Ó Conchúir, E., Holmström Olsson, H., Ågerfalk, P. J., & Fitzgerald, B. (2009)]. This model primarily contradicts with the 6th principle of the agile manifesto¹⁸ which states:

“The most efficient and effective method of conveying information to and within a development team is face-to-face conversation.”

Thus, apart from the mentioned contradiction, the model also inherits challenges from distributed software development models [Carmel, E., & Agarwal, R. (2001)] and introduces a new set of the same [Software Engineering Research and Practice, (2015)].

3.3.1 Challenges with Distributed Agile Software Development

Figure 3.4 depicts the impact of distance [Carmel, E., & Agarwal, R. (2001)] and its correlation between communication, control, and coordination.

Figure 3. 4: Impact of Distance [Carmel, E., & Agarwal, R. (2001)]

Here Coordination is the challenge of “managing interdependencies, uncertainties and equivocality, conflicts, technology representations, and their interrelations” [Wiredu, G. O. (2006)]. The control aspect can be split into two categories: formal and informal control [Moore, J. E., Williams, C. K., & Sumner, M. (2012)]. The self-organization of agile teams taps into the intrinsic motivation of team members and is a form of informal control. Communication, the coupling factor between coordination and control, is the exchange of information between a sender and a receiver to reach a mutual understanding. Figure 3.4 shows that distance directly

¹⁸ See <https://agilemanifesto.org/principles.html>

impedes coordination and control as well as indirectly through its restraining impact on communication, while the bold arrows between distance-communication-coordination, “represent the main challenge of distributed software development”.

On the other hand, Software Engineering Research and Practice, (2015) enlisted 13 challenges associated with the Distributed Agile software development. The same has also been referred to in various other journals [Hildenbrand, T., Geisser, M., Kude, T., Bruch, D., & Acker, T. (2008), Paasivaara, M., Durasiewicz, S., & Lassenius, C. (2008)].

Documentation

Agile teams do not give importance to the documentation [Shrivastava and Date, (2010)]. This may affect the distributed teams as they will miss some details about the project and hence their understanding of the project will suffer.

Pair Programming

One of the agile development methods uses pair programming in which two members of the team work on the same code side by side. This approach is very challenging in a distributed environment [Baheti, P., Gehringer, E., & Stotts, D. (2002)]. Hence distributed groups will have to find some other similar methodology.

Different Work Hours

A distributed team working in distinct continents has different time zones and thus their working hours don't match. Hence their working hours need to be aligned so that they can communicate with each other. This helps to avoid rework and provides clarity to the project.

Communication

Reduced communication has more effects in the case of distributed teams [Coordination Theory, Malone and Crowston, (1994), Smite et al., (2010)]. Most agile practices like test-driven development can be educated by providing one-on-one training. Many problems in distributed agile development are related to communication like unable to understand the customer, the system architecture, or system design. These have to be solved by participating in discussions or solving the problem manually.

Figure 3.5 illustrates communication channel complexity [Abilla, (2006)] i.e the team communication channel is dependent on team members in an agile team, thus the complexity is higher for large teams as compared to smaller teams. This complexity is denoted by the notation $(N \times (N - 1) / 2)$, where 'N' represents the number of team members.

Figure 3. 5: Communication Channel Complexity [Abilla, (2006)]

Knowledge Transition

Knowledge transition for the distributed team is highly dependent on various factors such as work hours, communication channels, documentation, etc [Espinosa, J. A., Slaughter, S. A., Kraut, R. E., & Herbsleb, J. D. (2007)]. As the related factors are already an existing challenge, it makes knowledge transition also a bit difficult for the teams working in different geographical locations.

Cultural Differences

Cultural issues can cause misunderstandings between team members. Several recent studies [Olson, J. S., & Olson, G. M. (2003), Abraham, L. R. (2009), Krishna, S., Sahay, S., & Walsham, G. (2004), Herbsleb, J., & Moitra, D. (2001)] have explored the cultural differences and measures to manage them in distributed teams. Some of the literature explicitly describes the challenges when interacting with Indian culture. This was very relevant for my thesis as Rabobank Payment domain comprises of Indian IT resources.

Team Cohesion

As agile development focuses on regular collaboration on all phases of the software project [Teasley, S., Covi, L., Krishnan, M., & Olson, J. (2002)], it gets worse when implementing distributed agile software development [Espinosa, J. A., Slaughter, S. A., Kraut, R. E., & Herbsleb, J. D. (2007)]. In the case of distributed development, members at distinctive locales are more averse to observe themselves as a major aspect of the same group when contrasted with co-placed members. The absence of togetherness, accompanied by a common view of goals, is an issue in that situation.

People vs. Process-Oriented Approaches

In co-located development, the process is people-oriented and informal methods [Casey, V., & Richardson, I. (2006)] are used to establish the control whereas distributed development needs the control to be achieved by formal methods [Shrivastava and Date, (2010)].

Knowledge Management

Knowledge management is crucial for success in distributed software development [Richardson et al., 2009]. During the development process the experience of team members, decisions, methods, and skills must be gathered through knowledge sharing. However, in the distributed agile software development model, knowledge sharing is difficult due to the lack of face-to-face communication between team members [Boden and Avram, (2009), Holz and Maurer, (2003)].

Language Barriers

The language problem arises when the teams are non-collocated and hence, they are not able to understand each other due to their different languages [Shrivastava and Date, (2010), Kajko-Mattsson et al. (2010)].

Role of Specialist

Typical software organizations always have people with specialized knowledge like business analysts, testers and user interface specialists, etc. Their knowledge is expected to be utilized in the project when needed. The agile methodology does not have any formal mechanism to request such expertise. Even if the specialists are brought, they may face problems similar to a new team member about gaining an

understanding of the project requirements [Banerjee, U., Narasimhan, E., & Kanakalata, N. (2011)].

Developer Fear of Skill Deficiency Exposure

Some developers fear that agile processes can bring forward their deficiencies. Onsite customers, stand-up meetings, use of storyboards, and whiteboards bring the shortcoming of developers in front of the whole team because agile methodology involves constant communication and collaboration. Besides, continuous integration and automated testing mean that developers can't hide poor, low-quality code. Exposing the weaknesses of developers can prove counterproductive [Conboy, K., Coyle, S., Wang, X., & Pikkarainen, M. (2011)].

Recruitment Challenges

It is difficult for agile companies to find the right people due to a lack of agile-specific recruitment policies. There are only a few universities or colleges that incorporate agile methods and skills into their programs. Moreover, degree programs tend to rely upon either technical or business skills but rarely involve both [Conboy, K., Coyle, S., Wang, X., & Pikkarainen, M. (2011)].

Hypothesis 3.2: It can thus be concluded that to have a better distributed agile software development, at one end, the 13 challenges must be acknowledged and worked upon by the organization along with the success factors associated with the 5 dimensions of agile software development to attain success in distributed agile software development. Chapter 6 will evaluate this with the help of a case study within the Rabobank Payment Domain.

Chapter 4
Team Performance

4 Team, Teamwork and Team Performance

A team can be defined as a social system of three or more people, which is embedded in an organization, whose members perceive themselves as such and are perceived as members by others (identity), and who collaborate on a common task (team-work) [Alderfer (1987), Hackman (1987), Wiendieck (1992), Guzzo and Shea (1992)]. They are usually organized hierarchically and sometimes dispersed geographically, they must integrate, synthesize, and share information; and they need to coordinate and cooperate as task demands shift throughout a performance episode to accomplish their mission [Salas et al., (2008)].

Teamwork on the other hand is defined as the interdependent components of performance required to effectively coordinate the performance of multiple individuals [Salas et al., (2008)].

Team performance is conceptualized as a multilevel process (and not a product) arising as team members engage in managing their individual and team-level task work and teamwork processes [Kozlowski & Klein, (2000)]. Team performance and team effectiveness [Singh, A. K., & Muncherji, N. (2007)] are often used synonymously in the literature; sometimes team performance is part of team effectiveness [Cohen and Bailey (1997)], and sometimes team effectiveness is part of team performance [Hoegl, M., & Gemuenden, H. G. (2001)]. Most of the models of team performance (or team effectiveness) originate from management science and psychology [Salas et al., (2008)].

4.1 Team Performance Factors

Many team performances models and teamwork frameworks describe teamwork quality (TWQ) and its relation to team performance in general [Hoegl, M., & Gemuenden, H. G. (2001), Mathieu et al. (2008), Cohen and Bailey (1997) and Rasmussen and Jeppesen (2006)]. Teamwork quality is a measure for the quality of collaboration in teams and consists of six facets: communication, coordination, the balance of member contributions, mutual support, effort, and cohesion. Figure 4.1 represents the six facets associated with teamwork quality and its positive influence and impact on team performance and personal success [Hoegl, M., & Gemuenden, H. G. (2001)].

Figure 4. 1: Teamwork Quality [Hoegl, M., & Gemuenden, H. G. (2001)]

Another literature [Dingsoyr, T., Faegri, T. E., Dyba, T., Haugset, B., & Lindsjorn, Y. (2016)], shows the team performance as an accumulation of five factors as depicted in figure 4.2.

Figure 4. 2: Team performance [Dingsoyr, T., Faegri, T. E., Dyba, T., et al. (2016)]

As figure 4.1 depicts a positive relation with team performance and figure 4.2 represents the factors associated with team performance, table 4.1 represents the common factors which, as per literature contribute to deciding team performance.

Team Work Quality	Team Performance	Remarks
Communication	Shared Mental Models	Mostly matched
Coordination	Team Coordination	Matched
Balance of Member contribution	Team Learning	Partially matched
Mutual Support	Team Learning	Partially matched
Effort		Implicit characteristic
Team Cohesion	Team Cohesion	Matched
	Goal Orientation	No match

Table 4. 1: Teamwork Quality vs Team Performance

It is very interesting to see that at one end team performance stresses on the goal orientation, whereas, teamwork quality doesn't cover that factor to uncover the team objective which is also very critical for the team [McGrath, (1984), Bunderson & Sutcliffe, (2003)].

Hypothesis 4.1: *It can thus be concluded that there is a very strong correlation between teamwork quality and team performance, and to address and evaluate team performance all the factors must be taken into account.*

4.2 Team Performance Model

There are various known team performance/team effectiveness models i.e. GRPI Model [Plovnick, Fry, and Rubin (1977)], Katzenbach and Smith Model [Katzenbach and Smith, (1993)], The T7 Model [Lombardo & Eichinger, (1995)], The LaFasto and Larson's Five Dynamics of Team Work [LaFasto & Larson, (2001)], The Hackman Model [Hackman (2002)], The Lencioni Model [Lencioni, P. M. (2010)], The Salas, Dickinson,

Converse and Tannenbaum Model [Salas, E., Dickinson, T.L., Converse, S.A. and Tannenbaum, S.I. (1992)] and Tuckman's FSNP Model [Tuckman (1965)] etc.

For depicting the phases of team performance, which is one of the key elements within my research, I chose Tuckman's FSNP Model [Tuckman (1965)] as depicted in figure 4.3 due to underlying reasons

1. It describes the development sequence in a phase-wise approach.
2. It is being used within Rabobank and everyone is familiar with this model including me.
3. Many models such as "GRPI Model" [Plovnick, Fry, and Rubin (1977)], "The T7 Model" [Lombardo & Eichinger, (1995)] and "The LaFasto and Larson's Five Dynamics of Team Work Model" [LaFasto & Larson, (2001)], focuses on processes for better team performance, they don't explicitly mention stage-wise approach to attain a particular team performance. These are good when attaining a better team performance on each stage of Tuckman's FSNP Model. Thus, by using Tuckman's FSNP Model, we can still avail of the benefits of other models.
4. There is a lot of similarity¹⁹ between Katzenbach and Smith's Model [Katzenbach and Smith, (1993)] and Tuckman's FSNP Model [Tuckman (1965)]. The "Team performance curve" of the Katzenbach and Smith Model depicts an identical representation of Tuckman's FSNP Model when the team becomes a high-performance team.

Figure 4. 3: Tuckman's FSNP Model [Tuckman (1965)]

¹⁹ See <https://www.praxisframework.org/en/library/katzenbach-and-smith>

Tuckman suggested that the life cycle of a team involves four stages. At each stage, the dynamics of the team change dramatically from periods of inefficiency and uneasiness through to a period of high performance. These changes are summarised in table 4.2 illustrated below

	Forming	Storming	Norming	Performing
General Observations	Uncertainty about roles, looking outside for guidance.	Growing confidence in the team, rejecting outside authority	Concern about being different, wanting to be part of the team	The concern with getting the job done
Content Issues	Some attempt to define the job to be done	Team members resist the task demands.	There is an open exchange of views about the team's problems	Resources are allocated efficiently; processes are in place to ensure that the final objective is achieved
Process Issues	Team members look outside for guidance and direction.	Team members deny the task and look for the reasons not to do it.	The team starts to set up the procedures to deal with the task.	The team can solve problems.
Feelings Issues	People feel anxious and are unsure of their roles. Most look to a leader or coordinator for guidance	People still feel uncertain and try to express their individuality. Concerns arise about the team hierarchy	People ignore individual differences and team members are more accepting of one another	People share a common focus, communicate effectively and become more efficient and flexible as a result

Table 4. 2: Phases of Tuckman's FSNP Model [Tuckman (1965)]

Even though this model has its own set of limitations [Bonebright, D. A. (2010)] and other models might be a better choice for helping a team attain better team performance. As the scope of this thesis is not to evaluate which model is the best-suited model for Rabobank, rather depicts various stages of team performance.

Hypothesis 4.2: *Thus, as per Tuckman, peak team performance can also be defined as a team that has undergone all phases of the Tuckman FSNP Model and resides at the performing stage.*

Chapter 5
Assessment of the Frameworks

5 Assessment of the Frameworks

A framework generally provides a skeleton abstraction of a solution to several problems that have some similarities. A framework is demonstrated using an exemplary set of maturity models [ECIS Proceedings (2011)] and will generally outline the steps or phases that must be followed in implementing a solution without getting into the details of what activities are done in each phase [Mnkandla, E. (2009)].

Since the Software Engineering Institute has launched the Capability Maturity Model [Paulk, M. (2002)] almost twenty years ago, hundreds of maturity models have been proposed by researchers and practitioners across multiple application domains.

As the main research question of this thesis is to identify the probable impact of distributed agile software development on team performance, this will be concluded and tested with the help of maturity models [Poeppebus, J., Niehaves, B., Simons, A., & Becker, J. (2011)]. The assessment will be carried out using the data of chapter 3, which enlists the factors contributing to the success of distributed agile software development and its associated challenges, and chapter 4, which highlights the factors contributing to team performance. These will further be mapped with the data collected via the case study performed within the Rabobank Payment domain and is further mentioned in Chapter 6.

5.1 Team Performance vs Team Maturity

Katzenbach and Smith conceptually defined the relationship between team performance and team maturity in *The Wisdom of Teams*²⁰: *Creating the High-Performance Organization* (1993). Figure 5.1 depicts the Katzenbach and Smith's "Team performance curve" model [Katzenbach and Smith, (1993)]. This model shows the correlation between team maturity and team performance.

Figure 5. 1: Team performance curve model [Katzenbach and Smith, (1993)]

²⁰ See Katzenbach, J. R. and Smith, D.K. (1993), *The Wisdom of Teams: Creating the High-performance Organisation*, Harvard Business School, Boston.

The importance of team maturity has also now been introduced in CHAOS 2020 report. Figure 5.2 depicts the tabular representation of the success ratio concerning team maturity. We can see in the table below that a highly mature team has a success rate of 66% and a failure rate of only 8%. On the other hand, an immature team garners a success rate of only 11% and fails at 35% of their projects.

Maturity Level	Successful	Challenged	Failed
Highly Mature	66%	26%	8%
Mature	46%	41%	13%
Moderately Mature	21%	58%	21%
Not Mature	11%	54%	35%

Chart 1.5: Resolution is OnTime, OnBudget, with satisfied customer. The results are based on 50,000 projects in the 2020 CHAOS database.

Figure 5. 2: CHAOS 2020 Report on the success rate of mature teams

Hypothesis 5.1: *Thus, as per Katzenbach and Smith’s “Team performance curve” model, team maturity is directly proportional to team performance or in other words, if team maturity is high, team performance will also be high. This is further supported by the CHAOS 2020 report which indicates that highly mature teams will result in a better success rate in software development within the organization. Hence to analyze team maturity, the usage of the maturity model becomes evident and essential.*

5.2 Maturity Models

Maturity can be regarded “as a measure to evaluate the capabilities of an organization regarding a certain discipline” [Rosemann & De Bruin (2005)]. Wikipedia²¹ states the Maturity Model as “Maturity is a measurement of the ability of an organization for continuous improvement in a particular discipline. The higher the maturity, the higher will be the chances that incidents or errors will lead to improvements either in the quality or in the use of the resources of the discipline as implemented by the organization.”

Maturity models are conceptual models that outline anticipated, typical, logical, and desired evolution path towards maturity [Becker & Knackstedt & Poeppebusch (2009)]. Maturity models can be understood as reference models [Herbsleb & Zubrow & Goldenson & Hayes & Paulk (1997)] and can be used to assess the as-is situation of an organization, to derive and prioritize improvement measures in terms of evolutionary stages [Iversen et al. (1999), Gottschalk (2009), Kazanjian & Drazin (1989)]. These distinctive stages provide a roadmap for improvement where each stage is superior to the previous stage [Mehta, Oswald, Mehta (2007), Subba Rao, Metts, Mora Monge (2003)]. This advancement on the evolution path means a step by step progression on team performance [Katzenbach and Smith, (1993)].

²¹ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maturity_model

5.2.1 Model Selection

For my master thesis, 80+ models²² are evaluated and analyzed by going through its literature, assessment methods, pros and cons, target audience, type of framework, and awareness within the organization with the help of relevant success stories. These models are then compared with Rabobank Payment Domain culture and way of working and final selection for appropriate models were concluded by getting the second opinion from the 2 agile coaches within the domain.

The Process

The models were analyzed by going through its literature and were then categorized into 5 dimensions i.e. Framework, Paid, Guidelines, Does Not Exist, and Assessment Tool. These Maturity Assessment tools/ Models/ Frameworks can be seen in Appendix 1 of this master thesis.

Frameworks: These comprised of models which talked about a systematic approach and had clear guidelines about each maturity levels. These models also had a provision of assessing the maturity of the organization in agile software development.

Paid: These comprised of models/tools which was a paid subscription, thus were eliminated for this master thesis.

Guidelines: These comprised of models/tools which only had guidelines on how to do things the correct way as per their viewpoint.

Does Not Exist: These were tools/models/frameworks which don't have any latest evidence of their existence.

Assessment Tools: These comprised of tools to assess the current maturity of an organization/ team/ individual via surveys/ games/ assessment methods/ checklists.

There might be more of such frameworks/assessment tools/models, which might be available and might even be used in various organization, however, for this master thesis the assessment tools/Models/Frameworks mentioned in Appendix 1 has been used and all analysis and literature study has been done only for them. Also, to identify the appropriate choice for this master thesis and to support the research question, the framework category was only selected as they only depicted a systematic phase of maturity levels which was aligning with the phases as discussed within the team performance chapter.

The Frameworks:

The analysis and evaluation of the 80+ Assessment tools/ Models/ Frameworks resulted in the selection of 11 free frameworks and is depicted in Table 5.1. These frameworks were thereafter re-evaluated based on Rabobank standards/ practices/ way of working/ feedback from agile coaches and finally combining them with the scope of the research question.

²² See <https://www.benlinders.com/tools/agile-self-assessments/>

Maturity Assessment tools/ Models/ Frameworks	Remarks	Selected for further analysis
Agile Adoption Framework by Ahmed Sidky	Not very clear on basic agile principles. Also not adhering to Rabobank principle i.e. Agile way of working in terms of timeline /process etc.	NO
Enterprise Agility Maturity Matrix by Eliassen Group	A good model combining Organization, team, process. Bit exhaustive and focuses on Enterprise level instead of domain level, thus eliminating it out.	NO
Agile Self-Assessment by Cape Project Management	A framework having an assessment method to evaluate the level of agile maturity within an organization. This model however emphasizes more on how efficiently the agile team (including stakeholders) is working w.r.t. Agile guidelines and principles.	NO
Agile Maturity Model (AMM) [Patel, C., & Ramachandran, M. (2009)]	A Software Process Improvement Framework for Agile Software Development Practices	YES
Squad Health Check model from Spotify / Henrik Kniberg ²³ [Rose, D. (2018)]	Mixed of the framework and a model to determine the health of a squad. A powerful model but is entirely based on input from people (management/coaches) who indicates how their squad is doing in several parameters.	YES
Agile Maturity Model by Jez Humble and Rolf Russell	A framework used internally within ThoughtWorks. This model focuses on processes within the organization	NO
Process Goals from Disciplined Agile (submitted by Scott W.Ambler)	A framework mentioning Disciplined Agile	NO
New SAFe Team Agility Self-Assessment by Scaled Agile	SAFE framework and assessment. As Rabobank doesn't follow SAFE methodology, this model is not selected for further evaluation.	NO
New Agile Software Product Line Automotive – Assessment Model (aspla) by Philipp Hohl	A framework and assessment for the automotive industry	NO
Agile Maturity Curve, French, M. (2018) ²⁴	A diagrammatic model depicting 5 levels of maturity with a defined scope for each level. Very similar to the Agile Maturity Model (AMM) by Chetan Kumar Patel and Muthu Ramachandran but with a dedicated focus on Agile elements only.	YES
Agile Fluency Model ²⁵	Agile Fluency Model. A model depicting phases of maturity level along with the minimum time needed to become an expert along with inputs needed from management.	YES

Table 5. 1: Agile Maturity Frameworks

²³ See <https://labs.spotify.com/2014/09/16/squad-health-check-model/>

²⁴ See www.scrum.org/resources, www.itweb.co.za/content/LPp6V7r45xaqDKQz

²⁵ See <https://www.agilefluency.org/>

The objective of this master thesis is to use the existing frameworks mentioned in Table 5.1 with its defined processes and principles without altering them and not creating any new maturity model framework. This master thesis also doesn't aim to discuss and illustrate all aspects/gaps of the mentioned models/frameworks rather it aims to highlight the most relevant gaps based on literature which prohibits this model to become an appropriate model choice for testing team performance using the maturity framework/model within Rabobank Payment Domain.

Agile Maturity Model (AMM):

The Agile Maturity Model (AMM) by Chetan Kumar Patel and Muthu Ramachandran [Patel, C., & Ramachandran, M. (2009)] is based on the agile software development values, practices, and principles. The AMM model is designed to improve and enhance the agile software development methodology and boost up the agile principles and objectives like the lower cost, customer satisfaction, and software quality. Figure 5.3 depicts the representation of the AMM model.

Figure 5. 3: Agile Maturity Model [Patel, C., & Ramachandran, M. (2009)]

The model provides a nice representation of different maturity levels along with activities, processes, and practices that must be attained to move to the next level. This model, however, has few drawbacks as derived by reading the literature which is enlisted below:

1. It is more of Capability Maturity Model Integration (CMMI) [Software Engineering Institute. (2010)] instead of the Agile Maturity model as the name suggests.
2. The model mentions some of the concepts such as projects, release planning, project plan, refactoring, project management and misses some core agile principles like feedback from the product owner, releasing shippable products thus making it a model which combines practices of Agile methodology to a

conventional iterative waterfall methodology, thus, not reflecting the core objective that was expected from Agile Maturity Model.

3. This model doesn't define the minimum time that must be spent to become expert on a particular level before moving to the next stage.

Hypothesis 5.2: Agile Maturity Model (AMM) can be a great maturity model for an organization that is still practicing both conventional methodologies as well as executing it using an agile way of working and its guidelines. However, for the Rabobank Payment domain, this model is not a good choice to be considered due to its scope which is not entirely restricted to the agile way of working in a distributed environment.

Squad Health Check:

Spotify²⁶, which is the initiator of Squad Health Check states “maturity models” as a model which involves in some sort of progression through different levels and has already been seen via the Agile Maturity Model. On the other hand, Squad Health Check model is a type of model which is usually benign and is for example intended for, managers or coaches in larger organizations who want to get a sense of focus areas for improvements, and help teams become more effective [Rose, D. (2018)]

Depicted in figure 5.4 are the 11 criteria on which the Squad Health Check is performed by the organization, with the status being Green, Yellow, and Red. Brief information about its interpretation is mentioned below

- **Green** doesn't mean perfect. It just means the squad is happy with this and see no major need for improvement right now.
- **Yellow** means some important problems need addressing, but it's not a disaster.
- **Red** means this needs to be improved.

This model which is referred to as Simplify@Scale at Rabobank is currently being used by the management to determine the health of their squads based on feedback from different teams. Squad Health Check helps the organization by providing health checks for Squad as well as people who are supporting it (especially managers, coaches, etc.). Thus, this is not a maturity model (also agreed within the literature) and intends to give guidance and direction for improvements within teams/squads.

²⁶ See <https://labs.spotify.com/2014/09/16/squad-health-check-model/>

Figure 5. 4: Squad Health Check [Rose, D. (2018)]

Hypothesis 5.3: *Squad Health Check can be a great model for management to see and evaluate the area for improvement based on feedback/on-ground observation. It also empowers the management to lead and take necessary actions/steps to ensure better squad health. However, this model still has gaps w.r.t. team contribution and how they can become the initiator and become self-facilitator and resolve the issues w.r.t. agile way of working themselves. As Rabobank already uses it, I would recommend the usability of this model only to identify improvement areas and compare the progress concerning squad's previous state and not for a derivation purpose about the agile health of the team.*

Agile Maturity Curve:

Agile maturity curve [French, M. (2018)] follows the top-down approach to define agile maturity. This model depicts several levels along with characteristics that are needed to be possessed at each level and in 5 different categories i.e. People, Process, Leadership, Structure, and Culture. Even though the Agile Maturity Curve is very much identical to Agile Maturity Model, it however only focuses on the processes/practices and guidelines of Agile methodology and expands the horizon to evaluating almost all dimensions of the success factor of the agile software development [Ramadan Darwish, N., & M. Rizk, N. (2015)] on its end goal.

Figure 5.5 depicts the mapping of the 5 dimensions of the success factors of agile software development with the dimensions within the agile maturity curve using evolutionary stages. Though the names of the 5 dimensions are not exactly aligned, their end objective is well aligned.

Figure 5. 5: Agile Maturity Curve

Hypothesis 5.4: Agile Maturity Curve can help organizations to focus on all aspects which are vital to growing as an agile organization as it directly incorporates the success factors associated with agile software development.

Despite the great value of this Maturity Model, it doesn't integrate all the challenges faced within distributed agile software development [Software Engineering Research and Practice, (2015)] within its stages efficiently and clearly. Thus, this model can help in deriving the maturity of a team but might not help determine the root cause to enhance the team maturity and also expects the team to have an agile mindset and culture before their evaluation.

Agile Fluency Model:

Agile Fluency Model²⁷, developed by Diana Larsen and James Shore in 2012 and substantially updated in 2018, is a framework to help teams understand their current position and to help them develop an individual road map and emphasizes on agile team's progress as they develop new capabilities. Agile teams pass through four distinct zones of fluency as they learn (fluency evolves). Diana Larsen defines fluency as things that you do automatically without thinking. Each zone brings specific benefits:

Focusing teams produce business value (agile fundamentals). The team thinks and plans in terms of the benefits their sponsors, customers, and users will see from their software.

Delivering teams deliver on the market cadence (agile sustainability). The team can release their latest work, at minimal risk and cost, whenever the business desires.

Optimizing teams lead their market (innovative business agility, agile promise). The team understands what their market wants, what your business needs, and how to meet those needs.

Strengthening teams make their organizations stronger (possible future of agile). The team understands its role in the larger organizational system and actively works to make that system more successful.

The model depicted in figure 5.6 gives a clear illustration based on

- Behaviors of teams at each level.
- How much time an organization must take to get matured at each level?
- What all investments must be taken by team/management to fulfill the requirements of each level?
- Supporting tools/methodology which can be utilized by the team for better productivity.

One of the articles "The Making of an Expert" [Harvard Business Review, (2006)], clearly emphasizes the importance of becoming an expert associating it with time and effort. The below phrase from the article summarizes the context in a very simple way

"It takes time to become an expert. Even the most gifted performers need a minimum of ten years of intense training before they win international competitions."

²⁷ See <https://www.agilefluency.org/>

Figure 5. 6: Agile Fluency Model

Hypothesis 3.7: *Agile Fluency Model is a mature model that defines a roadmap with an immense focus on gaining maturity in each zone/level, thereby developing new capabilities and helping the organization grow to become a profound Agile Organization.*

As the objective of this chapter is to evaluate existing Maturity Assessment tools/ Models/ Frameworks, concerning Rabobank’s culture and way of working, I have shortlisted 4 models i.e. Agile Maturity Model, Squad Health Check, Agile Maturity Curve, and Agile Fluency Model. Based on its literature and feedback from Agile coaches, the selection has been narrowed down to 2 models i.e. Agile Maturity Curve and Agile Fluency Model which will be used by me to analyze and draw a conclusion concerning the data collected for my case study research within Rabobank Payment Domain and is described within Chapter 6 of this thesis.

Chapter 6
Research Analysis

6 Case Study Research Method

As I have chosen single-case, holistic approach research method for my research, this chapter intends to execute the exploratory case study in Rabobank Payment Domain and test the same to find answers to my research question i.e. “

“What is the impact of distributed agile software development on team performance?”

6.1 Data Preparation

As the previous chapters 3 and 4, enlisted challenges and factors associated with distributed agile software development and team performance respectively, table 6.1 depicts the correlation between these independent and dependent variables [Recker, (2013)], i.e. distributed agile software development and team performance.

Challenges within Distributed Agile Software Development	Associated factor within Team Performance	Remarks
Documentation	Team Learning	Partially matched
Pair Programming	Team Learning	
Different Work Hours		Not addressed explicitly*
Communication	Team Coordination, Shared Mental Models	Partially matched
Knowledge Transition	Team Learning	
Cultural Differences		Identified gap*
Team Cohesion	Team Cohesion	
People vs. Process-Oriented Approaches		Identified gap*
Knowledge Management	Team Learning	
Language Barriers		Not addressed explicitly*
Role of Specialist	Team Learning	
Developer Fear of Skill Deficiency Exposure	Shared Mental Models	Partially matched
Recruitment Challenges	Team Learning	
	Goal Orientation	Identified gap*

Table 6. 1: Distributed Agile Software Development vs Team Performance

**Not addressed explicitly*: the referred challenge is part of one of the factor's property

**Identified gap*: This indicates that the challenge/factor is only present for one variable.

It can be seen that there is already a gap concerning team performance factors [Dingsoyr, T., Faegri, T. E., Dyba, T., Haugset, B., & Lindsjorn, Y. (2016)] and the challenges identified within distributed agile software development methodology [Software Engineering Research and Practice, (2015)]. All the challenges of distributed agile software development mentioned in table 6.1 which didn't find its co-related factor within team performance are directly or indirectly related with culture and its various aspects [Hall E. T., Beyond Culture, (1989), Wagner, (1995), Samovar, Porter, & McDa, (2009)].

This chapter will try to explore further this gap and see if this has any implication on team performance which is the objective of this research. I will try to explore it using the data collected for my case study within the Rabobank payment domain.

Now that a gap has been identified using literature associated with distributed agile software development and team performance, it is also important to evaluate if the selected maturity assessment model in chapter 5, can provide correct maturity of the team, hence giving us the data about team performance [Katzenbach and Smith, (1993)]. Table 6.2 tries to evaluate a few key questions and does a comparison between the selected maturity models for this thesis i.e. “Agile Maturity Curve” and “Agile Fluency Model”.

Parameters	Agile Maturity Curve	Agile Fluency Model
Is the model reflecting all 5 dimensions of the success factors of agile software development?	YES	Partially
Can each dimension have a different maturity level at a given point in time?	YES	NO
Does the model focus on becoming an expert in each stage?	NO	YES
Does this model give guidance on the minimum timeframe needed in each phase?	NO	YES
Is the model easy to implement?	YES	YES
Can the basic fundamental principle of team performance model like Tuckman be integrated with the maturity model?	YES	YES

Table 6. 2: Agile Maturity Curve vs Agile Fluency Model

It can be seen within table 6.2 that both these models have their own set of strengths and weakness, it is also interesting to see that even though agile maturity curve covers several parameters of the success factor of agile software development, it also poses an ambiguity and uncertainty to organizations when these dimensions don't reflect the maturity of a team unanimously i.e. the maturity of one dimension is different from the other one, thus its consequence to the organizations is not known. Also, this model expects a team to already possess an agile mindset and cultural shift before its evaluation as described in chapter 5. On the other hand, the agile fluency model mitigates these aspects in its stages.

As I don't intend to explore the consequence of the gap within agile maturity curve, which is not the objective of my research, this chapter will only try to explore further on this gap by making use of agile maturity curve as the selected maturity model since it evaluates maturity by using 5 categories which are also covered within the success factor of agile development model. This will thus help in evaluating the team performance for a distributed agile team of Rabobank Payment Domain.

6.2 Data Evaluation

For my research, the data has been collected using interviews, illustrated in Appendix 2 (including online survey) and agile process documents along with observation as already described within chapter 2. Table 6.3 shows the maturity levels of the

Rabobank Payment domain comprising of individual parameters and each category of the agile maturity curve, using the data collected from the mentioned three data collection methods and plotting them with the parameters of the agile maturity curve.

For my research, the scoring has been done using the Mean Descriptive statistics [Manikandan, S. (2011)] for all the data collected as a result of the interview using the formula

$$\text{Interview Mean Score, } \bar{x} = \frac{\sum x}{n1}$$

Where “**x**” is the number of correct answers given during the interview and “**n1**” is the total count of the person who was part of the survey and interview process. The maturity level is set at a range of 0.165 difference based on the interview mean score (m_1).

In addition to the mean descriptive statistics used to derive the maturity level of data collection method comprising of interviews, for observation and documentation, Likert²⁸ 2,3 and 5 point scale has also been used to derive the maturity level [Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S., & Pal, D. (2015)], which is equivalent to the response set value and is illustrated in table 6.3. The Likert scale was determined as a result of an interview with the agile coach, product owner, and delivery lead IT of Rabobank payment domain. For the interviews with team members, Likert 2 and 3 point scale have been used however for observation and documentation, Likert's 5 point scale has been used for calculation.

For the parameters comprising of multiple data collection methods, the average mean weight is used to calculate the maturity of the defined parameter using the formula

$$\text{Average Maturity Mean Score, } \bar{y} = \frac{\sum y}{n2}$$

Where “**y**” is the maturity value of each data collection method and “**n2**” is the number of data collection method used for the parameters of maturity assessment

<i>Parameters</i>	Maturity Level	Data Collection Method	Interview Mean Score	Likert 5-point scale
<i>People</i>				
<i>Adhering to all agile guidelines and practices</i>	2	Interview, Observation	0.39	Frequency (2)
<i>Agile training</i>	3	Documentation	NA	Quality (3)
<i>Role clarity</i>	3	Documentation	NA	Familiarity (3)
<i>Accountability to finish sprint</i>	2	Interview	0.35	
<i>Communication amongst individual</i>	2	Interview	0.33	

²⁸ See <https://www.simplypsychology.org/likert-scale.html>

<i>Ceremonies to celebrate success</i>	2	Observation, Documentation	NA	Frequency (2), Familiarity (2)
<i>Individual Ownership on handling impediments</i>	3	Interview, Observation	0.50	Frequency (3)
<i>T-shaping</i>	2	Documentation	NA	Quality (2)
<i>Emphasis on code reviews and documentation</i>	1	Interview	0.21	
Mean Average	2			
Process				
<i>Fixed Budget</i>	1	Interview	0.16	
<i>Fixed scope</i>	1	Interview	0.17	
<i>Final product delivery after each sprint</i>	2	Interview, Documentation	0.26	Quality (2)
<i>Defined/documented quality assurance process</i>	4	Interview, Documentation	0.66	Quality (3)
<i>Team cadence</i>	3	Interview	0.53	
<i>The process to coordinate across multiple teams</i>	2	Documentation	NA	Familiarity (2)
<i>Discuss defects/incidents for knowledge sharing and constructive feedback</i>	2	Interview, Observation	0.32	Frequency (2)
<i>Accuracy of requirements by business</i>	2	Interview, Documentation	0.17	Quality (2)
Mean Average	2			
Leadership				
<i>Providing support to agile teams</i>	4	Observation, Documentation	NA	Frequency (4), Quality (3)
<i>Transparency in the agile process and objectives</i>	4	Observation, Documentation	NA	Frequency (4), Quality (4)
<i>Establishing KPIs for agile teams</i>	3	Documentation	NA	Quality (3)
<i>Involvement of product owner with an Agile team</i>	3	Interview	0.47	
<i>Management involvement with the team</i>	4	Interview	0.66	
<i>Supporting teams by providing the necessary infrastructure needed for agile transformation</i>	3	Interview	0.56	
Mean Average	4			
Structure				
<i>Business and IT part of one team</i>	4	Documentation	NA	Familiarity (4)
<i>Product owner having strong business knowledge</i>	3	Interview	0.50	

<i>Static team members within the scrum team</i>	1	Interview	0.04	
<i>Involvement of COEs within teams/domain</i>	4	Documentation	NA	Familiarity (4)
<i>A governance framework to check team health/status</i>	4	Interview	0.66	
<i>Documented team hierarchy</i>	4	Documentation	NA	Familiarity (4)
Mean Average	3			
Culture				
<i>Social cohesion</i>	2	Observation	NA	Frequency (2)
<i>Team coordination</i>	3	Interview	0.53	
<i>Task cohesion</i>	4	Interview	0.73	
<i>Sharing the responsibility of the team member's task</i>	3	Observation	NA	Frequency (3)
<i>Awareness of business strategy of the tribe</i>	2	Interview	0.33	
<i>Enthusiasm on team building activities</i>	2	Interview	0.30	
<i>Ability to challenge the business on requirements</i>	1	Interview	0.13	
<i>Process of integrating new team members</i>	1	Observation, Documentation	NA	Frequency (2), Familiarity (1)
<i>Process of rewarding team members/team</i>	2	Observation	NA	Frequency (2)
Mean Average	2			

Table 6. 3: Maturity assessment (Rabobank Payment Domain, Appendix 2))

The data shown in table 6.3 shows an accumulated mean/average maturity of **2.6** based on the 5 categories as mentioned in the agile maturity curve for the Rabobank payment domain. It is also important to notice that the categories don't have a uniform distribution of the maturity level and shows a standard deviation (σ_x) of 0.89. Thus, it is difficult to infer if distributed agile software development does have any impact on team performance or not. Therefore, inferential statistics test needs to be conducted to get the answer to the main research question by comparing the statistics of the co-located software development team and distributed agile software, development teams.

Table 6.4 shows overall scoring based on interviews and online surveys using a Likert 2,3 and 5-point scale [Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S., & Pal, D. (2015)], w.r.t team maturity for the co-located software development team and distributed agile software development team. As the co-located team is of two variants i.e. co-located agile team with cultural diversity and co-located team without cultural diversity, table 6.4 shows the categorization of maturity score based on these variants only for representational purpose. Along with the scoring, the table shows mean and variance using the formula

$$\text{Mean value, } \bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$$

Where, “ x_i ” is the total score of the team based on the online survey and interview and “ n ” is the number of samples taken for the calculation. Variance is also calculated using formula

$$\text{Variance, } \sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}$$

Where, “ x_i ” is the value of each sample, “ \bar{x} ” is the mean value of individual teams and “ n ” is the total number of samples considered for executing the inferential statistical test. As I intend to do an inferential statistical test using only two groups' i.e. co-located team and distributed agile team, the splitting of the co-located agile team will not be considered as two groups rather will be taken collectively to perform the inferential statistical test.

Co-located Software Development Teams		Distributed Agile Software Development Teams
Without Cultural Diversity	With Cultural Diversity	
73	44	34
79	48	37
	48	39
	54	43
	57	45
	58	45
	59	45
	61	46
	69	46
		47
		48
		49
Total Samples (n1) = 11 Average/Mean (\bar{x}_1) = 59.09 Variance (σ_1^2) = 119.69		Total Samples (n2) = 12 Average/Mean (\bar{x}_2) = 43.67 Variance (σ_2^2) = 21.33

Table 6. 4: Agile Team's maturity scoring (Appendix 2)

As the maturity values are normally distributed and table 6.4 can clearly show a difference in the average/mean for both the teams, thus, to get the answer to my research question, I will be executing a parametric test [Sedgwick, P. (2015)] by evaluating the maturity of co-located software development agile teams and distributed agile software, development teams.

6.2.1 Parametric Statistical Hypothesis Test

A statistical hypothesis test [Emmert-Streib, F., & Dehmer, M. (2019)] is a method of statistical inference²⁹. For performing the Parametric Statistical Hypothesis Test, two

²⁹ See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Statistical_inference

statistical data sets need to be compared and the necessary hypothesis (null hypothesis (H_0) and alternate hypothesis (H_a)) will be validated and tested. Thus, the hypothesis (H_0 and H_a) that I will be validating are,

H_0 : The maturity of a distributed agile team and co-located agile team are identical, thus, a distributed agile team does not have any impact on team performance.

H_a : The maturity of the co-located agile team different from the maturity of a distributed agile team, thus, the distributed agile team does have an impact on team performance.

To do the hypothesis test, we calculate the probability (P-value) to conclude. The “**P**” value (or the calculated probability) is the probability of the event occurring by chance if the null hypothesis is true. The “**P**” value is numerical between 0 and 1 and is interpreted in deciding whether to reject or retain the null hypothesis. Table 6.5 depicts the correlation of this “**P**” value concerning the null hypothesis and alternate hypothesis.

P-Value	Result	Null Hypothesis (H_0)
< 0.01	Result is highly significant	Reject (null hypothesis) H_0
≥ 0.01 but < 0.05	Result is significant	Reject (null hypothesis) H_0
≥ 0.05	The result is not significant	Don't Reject (null hypothesis) H_0

Table 6. 5: P-value interpretation [Emmert-Streib, F., & Dehmer, M. (2019)]

As the null hypothesis and alternate hypothesis has now been defined, the next step is to figure out the type of parametric test that will be suitable for my research. Due to the nature of data as depicted in table 6.4, which comprises of the maturity assessment of the teams of Rabobank Payment Domain in two distinct categories i.e. one category comprising of the maturity assessment of co-located software development agile teams and other category comprising of the maturity assessment of distributed agile software development teams, I will be executing the hypothesis test using “Student’s Two-Sample Unpaired t-test”.

Student’s Two-Sample Unpaired t-test:

Student’s t-test³⁰, in statistics, a method of testing hypotheses about the mean of a small sample drawn from a normally distributed population when the population standard deviation is unknown. As the unpaired test can be of two types i.e. t-test with equal variance and t-test with unequal variance, it is important first to identify the type to proceed ahead in executing Student’s Two-Sample Unpaired t-test. Table 6.6 depicts the process of determining the type of unpaired t-test to be used, by using data present in table 6.4.

Here, “n” is the total number of samples taken for calculation, “ x_i ” is the value of each sample i.e. maturity assessment score.

³⁰ See <https://www.britannica.com/science/Students-t-test>

Steps	Formula	Value of Co-located Agile team	Value of Distributed Agile team
Number of entries	Count(n)	n1=11	n2=12
Calculate Mean (\bar{x})	$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n x_i}{n}$	$\bar{x}_1 = 59.09$	$\bar{x}_2 = 43.67$
Calculate Variance (σ^2)	$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}$	$\sigma_1^2 = 119.69$	$\sigma_2^2 = 21.33$
Calculate Degree of freedom	df _i = n-1	df ₁ = 10	df ₂ = 11
Generic Values			
Probability (α)	$\alpha = 0.05$ (default)		
Calculate F _{stat}	F _{stat} = High σ^2 / Low σ^2	119.69/21.33 = 5.61	
Validate F _{crit} ³¹	Validate from F-distribution table using df _(10,11) and $\alpha = 0.05$ *Refer Appendix 3	2.85	

Table 6. 6: Process to determine the type of unpaired t-test

Finally, the data of F_{stat} (F statistics) and F_{crit} (F critical), need to be compared to derive the result. As the value of F_{stat} > F_{crit}, I will be executing the hypothesis test using "Student's Two-Sample Unpaired t-test assuming unequal variance³²".

Now that the hypothesis test which will be used to execute my research to get the answer to my research question has been identified, Student's Two-Sample Unpaired t-test assuming unequal variance is depicted along with the values in table 6.7 using the maturity scores defined in table 6.4. Now that I am trying to first establish a hypothesis about the probable impact of a distributed agile team on team performance, the two-tail test result must be considered for deciding which hypothesis holds true.

Sno.	Steps	Formula	Result
1	Calculate t-statistic (t _{stat})	$t_{stat} = \frac{(\bar{x}_1 - \bar{x}_2)}{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}}}$ <p> \bar{x}_1: Mean of Co-located agile team \bar{x}_2: Mean of the Distributed agile team n1: A sample size of the Co-located agile team n2: A sample size of the Distributed agile team σ_1^2: Variance of the Co-located agile team σ_2^2: Variance of the Distributed agile team </p>	t _{stat} = 4.33
2	Calculate Degree of freedom (df)	$df = \frac{\left(\frac{\sigma_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{n_2}\right)^2}{\frac{(\sigma_1^2)^2}{(n_1-1)} + \frac{(\sigma_2^2)^2}{(n_2-1)}}$	df = 13
3	Fetch t-critical (t _{crit})value from t-table ³³	Probability (α) = 0.05 df = 13	One-tail: t _{crit} = 1.77 Two-tail:

³¹ See http://www.socr.ucla.edu/Applets.dir/F_Table.html

³² See <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Variance>

³³ See <https://www.sjsu.edu/faculty/gerstman/StatPrimer/t-table.pdf>

		*Refer appendix 3	$t_{crit} = 2.16$
4	Compare t_{stat} and t_{crit}		$t_{stat} > t_{crit}$
5	Derive p-value from t-table for df_{13}	p-value = value (df_{13}) closest to t_{stat} *Refer appendix 3	One-tail: p-value < 0.0004 Two-tail: p-value < 0.0008

Table 6. 7: Student's Two-Sample Unpaired t-test assuming unequal variance

As P-value interpretation (Table 6.5) depicts that if the “**p-value**” is less than “**0.01**”, the result is highly significant and that the null hypothesis (**H₀**) must be rejected. The same is also confirmed by looking at the comparison of “**t_{stat}**” and “**t_{crit}**”, where the “**t_{stat}**” value is greater than “**t_{crit}**”, re-confirming the conclusion drawn based on “**p-value**”. Thus, the alternate hypothesis holds for my research, which is,

H_a: The maturity of the co-located agile team different from the maturity of a distributed agile team, thus, the distributed agile team does have an impact on team performance.

6.3 Limitations

As the data collected for this research was a self-assessment done by using online questionnaires and was to analyze the maturity of the agile teams (rather than a fact-based audit), so the quality of the answers relies predominantly on the sincerity of the respondents. In addition to this, as the questions were not covering all parameters present in the agile maturity curve, the same was mitigated with the use of interviews.

I also had intended to have 2nd round of interviews to get answers on a broader set of questions related to my thesis, however, due to COVID 2019, I didn't get enough support and time from various agile teams in executing the 2nd round of interviews, thus, the set of samples were restricted to 23. I was also aware that the sample size of 23 was too little to any sort of complex data statistical test, therefore I chose to perform Student's t-test as it is the only data statistical test that can support a lesser sample size to draw any sort of inference.

In addition to this, due to privacy and confidential reasons, the detailing about the documentation name and its usage has not been added in this thesis, instead, only the Likert 5 point scale score has been used to determine the maturity of Rabobank Payment domain. This however was not used while executing the hypothesis test instead, Likert 2 and 3 point scales were only being used for determining the maturity level of co-located teams and distributed agile teams for the hypothesis test.

6.4 Data Conclusion

Based on the outcome from data evaluation, where the “Student's Two-Sample Unpaired t-test assuming unequal variance” proves that the alternative hypothesis holds. Also, as the value of the mean/average was higher in the case of the co-

located agile teams ($mean=58.90$), it does prove that the maturity of the co-located agile team is better than that of a distributed agile team ($mean= 43.67$). The same can be confirmed with the help of the one-tail t-test result, where the “ t_{stat} ” value is greater than “ t_{crit} ”. Hence team performance for the co-located agile teams is better than that of distributed agile teams.

This difference in maturity level between the co-located agile team and distributed agile can very well be justified by my observation as depicted in “*Table 6.1: Distributed Agile Software Development vs Team Performance*”.

The table tried to identify the gaps between the challenges of distributed agile team and team performance factors, which were

- Different work hours
- Cultural Differences
- People vs. Process-Oriented Approaches
- Language Barriers
- Goal Orientation

These identified gaps seem to be the decisive factor why such variations were observed between the distributed agile team and co-located agile team because all these gaps seem to be more applicable along with higher impact for distributed agile teams as compared to the co-located agile teams.

Chapter 7

Conclusion, Recommendation and Further Research

7 Conclusion

As my research question intended to identify the impact of distributed agile software development on team performance, the "Student's Two-Sample Unpaired t-test assuming unequal variance", clearly provides below-mentioned conclusions,

- As the p-value in the Student's Two-Sample Unpaired t-test assuming unequal variance was way less than 0.01, it statistically proved that co-located agile teams had better maturity/team performance as compared to distributed agile teams. The same can be confirmed with the help of the one-tail t-test result, where the " t_{stat} " value was greater than " t_{crit} ". Thus, I strongly believe that there is a negative impact of distributed agile software development on team performance.
- The gaps identified between the challenges of a distributed agile team and team performance factors i.e. "Different work hours, Cultural Differences, People vs. Process-Oriented Approaches, Language Barriers and Goal Orientation", does play a vital role in justifying the variation in maturity/team performance between co-located agile teams and distributed agile teams as these identified gaps are more visible in distributed teams as compared to the co-located teams.
- Assessing maturity using just a single maturity assessment model can give inconclusive results because of the non-uniform maturity level across various categories as observed within this research. Such inconclusive results might lead to wrong interpretation of maturity level of the team, thus leading to a perception challenge between agile team and management as it was visible in the maturity assessment, where at one end leadership and structure scored a maturity level of 4, and on other hand, people, process and culture scored a maturity score of 2. This can lead to the organization not believing in current agile methodology implementation and can lead to making decisions that can impact them financially as well as impacting the morale of teams. Thus, the combination of the maturity assessment model along with the agile fluency model can help in minimizing this impact. The same has been illustrated in detail within the recommendation section of this chapter.

7.1 Recommendation

As the agile maturity curve was not able to have a uniform distribution of the maturity score throughout its category, using just one model for evaluating the team might not be helpful to the organization as mentioned in the conclusion section of this chapter.

- Thus, I would recommend making use of both agile maturity curve which gives strength to maturity assessment by covering the 5 categories associated with an organization i.e. People, Process, Leadership, Structure and Culture, and, agile fluency model, which can ensure that teams (including leadership), spends minimum time within one phase to become an expert thus adapting the agile way of working as a culture. By integrating both these powerful assessment

tools/frameworks, I do believe that the assessment will have a uniformity thus helping the organization to focus on the areas which need attention.

- Each phase/level of the maturity model can also be sub-categorized by using the performance model like Tuckman. This approach might help the agile team in improving their maturity efficiently and can also act as a bridge when integrating the maturity model with the agile fluency model.
- Even though the maturity model has fixed categories, I would recommend amending it by adding the gaps which were identified between the challenges of a distributed agile team and team performance factors. These gaps, when added to the maturity assessment can help the team to act proactively in improving the team performance score/maturity score of the distributed agile software development team.

7.2 Further Research

As the maturity assessment showcased a non-uniform distribution of the maturity score across its categories, I would recommend for future students to execute a research to check the implication to organizations when they assess their team using just a single model, which shows similar characteristics i.e. multiple levels having varying maturity scores. Can this be a potential reason which is observed within the organization that tries to implement several methodologies in a quick period?

In addition to this, as I had executed "Student's Two-Sample Unpaired t-test assuming unequal variance" for two samples i.e. co-located agile team and distributed agile team, however in my data which I depicted in table 6.4 Agile Team maturity scoring, the co-located agile team was split for illustration purpose in two categories i.e. co-located team with cultural diversity and co-located team without cultural diversity. It can also be good research to find an impact of these two categories of a co-located agile team on team performance and associated factors that play a vital role in contributing to a better maturity score.

7.3 Discussion

This research has been done taking Rabobank Payment domain as the case study with the conclusion being derived based on the surveys and interviews with the team members and leadership of the same domain. The conclusion thus, might not hold true for other organizations, however, if an organization has a similar structure i.e. distributed agile software development model having people from The Netherlands and India (south region), this research can very well be replicated to evaluate the outcome for their respective domain/organization.

I also would like to re-state that for my research, the maturity assessment model chosen was the agile maturity curve and its specific 5 categories of evaluation. Hence, if any other assessment framework is chosen, the maturity assessment must be done as per its specific guideline which might result in a varying outcome thus, not aligning with this research's outcome and conclusion.

REFLECTION

When I look back at the result of this research I do believe and feel that I have learned many things on the basic essence and concept behind doing research. Coming from an organization where the approach has always been output-oriented, it did take a lot of time for me to understand that research can't be written keeping output in mind, rather research can have an output unjustified and unknown or even justified and proven. This core principle did take a considerable amount of my time, and if I need to re-write research I would first come out of the mindset of writing something which I want to achieve/prove rather write thesis whose outcome is yet unknown.

A literature study has always been the base for doing research but I do believe that the concept of research method and all literature study across the method (data analysis and data inference) can be very helpful as I did had to go back to literature when my data was inconclusive and found new works of literature which I can use for the type of data analysis I was doing in my research. If I would have done earlier, it could have helped me structure my thesis well with lesser effort and would have been in line with the data analysis upfront.

I do believe there is learning hidden in every work we do, and these learning that I explored in the journey of this MEITA program and the thesis writing has enabled me to think like a researcher and questioning self before concluding to any circumstances.

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APPENDIX

APPENDIX 1

Maturity Assessment tools/Models/Frameworks:

Maturity Assessment tools/Models/Frameworks	Framework	Paid	Guidelines	Does Not Exist	Assessment Tool	Remarks
My Agile Self-Assessment Game and my book The Agile Self-assessment Game		X				
The Scrum Checklist from Henrik Kniberg			X			
42 point test: How Agile are You by Kelly Waters					X	
Questions for Transitioning to Agile from Johanna Rothman					X	
Agile Adoption Framework by Ahmed Sidky	X					https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0704/0704.1294.pdf Not very clear on basic agile principles. Not adhering to Rabobank principle og
Team Barometer by Jimmy Janlén					X	
Scrum Checklist by Boris Gloger			X			
Corporate Agile 10-point checklist by Elena Yatzeck			X			
Joe's Unofficial Scrum Checklist by Joe Little			X			
Lean-Agile Roadmap by NetObjectives				X		
ScrumButt Test aka the Nokia Test by Jeff Sutherland					X	
How to Measure Team Agility by Len Lagestee					X	To check sprint completion health and team composition health
Scrum Assessment Series by David Hawks			X			
Agile Maturity Self Assessment by Robbie Mac Iver					X	A mentioning of different agile levels and what qualities team/organization should possess. Not very clear and lacked several aspects
Enterprise Agility Maturity Matrix by Eliassen Group	X					Good model combining Organization, team, process. Bit exhaustive and focuses on Enterprise level instead of domain
Enterprise Agile Practice Assessment Tool (paid services) by DrAgile		X				
Comparative Agility by Mike Cohn and Kenny Rubin		X				Consulting company thus payable
Open Assessments from scrum.org			X		X	It is more about scrum guidelines for
Readiness & Fit Analysis from the Software Engineering Institute by Suzanne Miller			X			
Agile Journey Index by Bill Krebs			X		X	Assessment tool based on dynamic questions. Tough to realize for this master thesis. It also only focuses on technology and process motly and has
Seven Questions to Ask to Determine if Your Organization is Agile Ready from PMI		X				
An Organizational Transformation Checklist by Michael Sahota					X	Very basic assessment
Agile Maturity Matrix in JIRA by Atlassian					X	Tool integrated with Jira and also being used by Enterprise Agility Maturity Matrix
Assessing your Client's Agility by Marcel Britsch					X	A good tool but can be beneficial during start of agile implementation
Borland Agile Assessment					X	assessment survey used within Borland and inspired by Nokia test. Focuses on 12 questions to determine current maturity
Agile Self Assessment by Cape Project Management	X				X	A framework having an assessment method to evaluate the level of agile maturity within organization. This model however emphasizes more on how efficiently agile team (including
Agile Maturity Model (AMM) by Chetankumar Patel and Muthu Ramachandran	X					A Software Process Improvement framework for Agile Software
Test your Organisation's Agile Credentials by Storm-Consulting					X	Survey by a consulting company
Depth of Kanban by Christophe Achouiantz					X	It is more of a coaching tool
Agile Essentials (card game) by Ivar Jacobson International			X			It is a basic starter kit toolbox that covers all the common and critical aspects of
IBM DevOps Practices Self Assessment					X	More about DevOps instead of Agile
Agile team evaluation by Eric Gunnerson					X	Fixed set of questions to determine how well a team is doing in Agile way of
Ready for Agile Part 1 and Part 2 by Salah Elleithy (based on research by Ahmed				X		
Squad Health Check model from Spotify / Henrik Kniberg	X					Mixed of framework and a model to determine the health of a squad. A powerful model but is entirely based on input from people
Assessing the level of Agility by Yuval Yeret					X	An assessment to determine current
Assess your Agility by James Shore					X	An assessment tool explicitly to evaluate the XP used within Agile organization.
Test Maturity card game by Joep Schuurkes and Huib Schoots					X	An assessment game to evaluate agile
AgilityHealth Radar (paid service)		X				
Rojooms How Deep is your Agile? by Shirly Ronen-Harel					X	Uses Agile maturity model to evaluate
Agile 3R Model of Maturity Assessment by Phani Thimmapuram				X		
Cargo Cult Agile Checklist by Age of Product			X			
Success Factors for Self-Assessment of Teams by Angelika Drach, Christoph Mathis				X		

Maturity Assessment tools/Models/Frameworks	Framework	Paid	Guidelines	Does Not Exist	Assessment Tool	Remarks
Your Path through Agile Fluency by Diana Larsen and James Shore & Finding Agile That's Fit-for-Purpose by Diana Larsen	X					Agile Fluency Model
The InfoQ Minibook Scrum Hard Facts: Roles, Artifacts, All meetings provides a			X			Scrum guidelines
The InfoQ minibook An Agile Adoption and Transformation Survival Guide includes a checklist for change agents		X				
Organizational Agile Transformation by LeadingAgile		X				Consulting company
Agile Maturity Self-Assessment Survey by Eduardo Ribeiro				X		
Implementing Lean Software Development (Poppendieck)		X				
Xebia essentials (free app)					X	Game to evaluate maturity. Payable to
XebiaLabs DevOps Self-Assessment		X				
Teammetrics by Christiaan Verwijs					X	Assessment done wrt Scrum
Agile Assessment by Piotr Nowinski				X		
Assess your agile engineering practices by Corinna Baldauf					X	Not very clear and focuses only on 5
Agile Maturity Model by Jez Humble and Rolf Russell	X					A framework used internally within ThoughtWorks. This model focuses
Maturity Assessment Model for Scrum Teams by Marmamula Prashanth Kumar				X		
The Joel Test: 12 Steps to Better Code by Joel Spolsky					X	Assessment tool for better code quality
Back-of-a-Napkin Agile Assessment by Elisabeth Hendrickson					X	A 10 point checklist to know agile
Are you really agile? by People10					X	Detailed assessment on infrastructure, project management,
Process Goals from Disciplined Agile (submitted by Scott W. Ambler)	X					A framework mentioning Disciplined Agile
Scrum Master Checklist by Michael James			X			
Top 20 self assessment questions by Gene Gendel					X	An assessment before deciding to become Agile
Project Approach Questionnaire by Agile Business Consortium		X				
Visual Management Self-Assessment by Ben Hogan (free subscription required)					X	An assessment tool for evaluating the Kanban adoption.
Lean Agile Intelligence by Michael McCalla (free tool, registration required)	X	X	X		X	Need training to get accustomed to understand this
Continuous Delivery Maturity Checklist by DZone					X	An assessment tool for technology aspect of organization.
The Agendashift™ values-based delivery assessment by Mike Burrows (commercial service with free mini edition)		X				
Retropoly by Sorin Sfirlogea and Florian Georgescu					X	A game to assess agile practice.
How Agile Are You? by Mark Balbes					X	An assessment focusing on 12 agile
Quick self-assessment of your organization's agility by Signet / Charles Parry					X	An assessment tool to determine agility in organization with 22 questions.
Agile Software Development Complete Self-Assessment (paid service)		X				
DevOps Self-Assessment by Microsoft in collaboration with DevOps Research and Assessment (DORA) – Registration required					X	DevOps assessment tool
Health Monitors from the Atlassian Team Playbook					X	A basic assessment tool with 8 questions
Kanban Service Maturity Assessment by Gerard Chiva				X		
fluent@agile game by Peter Antman and Christian Vikström					X	An assessment game to evaluate team's current state in agile journey
Agile Alert by H&Z		X			X	An assessment to evaluate team's current state in agile journey by
New Team Agility Self Assessment by Yodiz					X	An assessment to determine team agility
New SAFE Team Agility Self-Assessment by Scaled Agile	X				X	SAFE framework and assessment
New Agile Software Product Line Automotive – Assessment Model (aspla) by	X				X	A framework and assessment for organization to become agile
New Business Agility Manifesto – Diagnostics by Roger T. Burlton, Ronald G. Ross					X	
New Agile Assessment by AgileTrailblazers (paid service)		X				
New Enterprise Business Agility Maturity Assessment by Eduardo Ribeiro					X	A good assessment survey but comprises of 53 questions which are very difficult to
New Measure.team by Kelly Albrecht					X	An assessment to determine team agility
New Detecting Agile BS by US Department of Defense (DoD)					X	An assessment to determine team agility in department of defence
New Skills Self-Assessments by BPMInstitute.org					X	An assessment to evaluate team's current state in agile journey by
New Agile Adoption Interview by PLADcloud					X	An assessment to evaluate if team practices the agile principles correctly or
New Agility Assessment by RefineM					X	An assessment to evaluate if team practices the agile principles correctly or
Agile Maturity Curve	X					A diagrammatic model depicting 5 levels of maturity with a defined scope for each level. Very similar with the Agile Maturity Model (AMM) by Chetankumar Patel and Muthu Ramachandran but with a dedicated focus on Agile elements only.

APPENDIX 2

Survey Result –Product Owner, Delivery Manager IT, Agile Coach

Timestamp	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/19
Survey Questions	Response 1	Response 2	Response 3	Response 4	Response 5	Response 6
Name/designation of the person	Product Owner	Delivery Manager IT	Agile Coach	Product Owner	Delivery Manager IT	Product Owner
As per you, how would you rank your team in Agile Maturity?	3	4	2	2	2	3
Are your teams sometimes working on fixed timeline requirements?	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Do you entertain fixed timeline requirements?	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Do you have a fixed IT budget concept within your tribe?	Unaware	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Do you regularly interact with Scrum Master to evaluate progress/concern of the team?	Always	Always	Sometimes	Sometimes	Always	Always
Do you have any governance framework to check team health/progress?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
How often do you think Rabobank reuses existing knowledge and not reinvent?	Sometimes	Never	Always	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes
Are all product owners within your tribe part of the same domain already for substantial years?	Mostly	Sometimes	Always	Sometimes	Always	Always
How often do you observe a proactive approach from the team in case of impediments?	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes	Always
How often do you have status meetings with Product Owners?	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly
As per you, how informed are the Product owners in terms of Sprint status?	Totally aware	Totally aware	Totally aware	Totally aware	Totally aware	Totally aware
As per you, who is Accountable when a Scrum team is not performing well?	Team	Product owner	All	All	Team	All
How would you rank team coordination within your area/tribe?	3	3	3	3	2	2
How would you rate the importance of cultural integration within your team?	5	5	5	5	5	4
How would you rank your team wrt the business strategy of the tribe?	2	2	2	3	4	2
When implementing a new way of working, is the maturity of the team evaluated?	Sometimes	Always	Never	Sometimes	Sometimes	Sometimes
Do you have standard processes for quality control?	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Do you feel technical documentation is important for better maintainability?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
As management what do you think are 3 essential elements for better team performance?	feedback, goal orientation, positive and open atmosphere, proactive	understanding why(goal orientation), respect, feedback, mutual consent	purpose (goal orientation), autonomous team, T shaping	trust, utilizing experience, develop as a team (T shaping), developing in maturity	team alignment, agreements about requirements, good scrum masters, need for PM	leadership, transparent strategy

Survey Result –Agile Teams

The team score is the result of accumulation of scores for individual answer for each question. For individual question's scoring, Likert 2 point (Yes and No) and Likert 3 point (Always, Sometimes and Never) has been used.

Timestamp	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/19	2019/12/20	2019/12/20	2019/12/20
Team Scores	39 / 100	45 / 100	44 / 100	48 / 100	37 / 100	46 / 100	48 / 100	59 / 100
Survey Questions/Score	RESPONSES							
Does your colleague(s) need a reminder for daily standup?	Yes 0/3	Yes 0/3	No 3/3	No 3/3	No 3/3	No 3/3	Yes 0/3	No 3/3
Is your Product Backlog sorted by the Product Owner?	Never 0/3	Sometimes 1/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3
Does your team gain mutual consent(after discussion) before finalizing the story points?	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5
How many times does your team manage to achieve a story point?	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Always 4/4	Always 4/4	Never 0/4	Always 4/4	Sometimes 2/4	Always 4/4
DEMO involving working product	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you encounter a story with a fixed timeline?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 5/5
Have your team members changed(added/replaced) in the last 2 years within your team?	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10
How often are the action items of the previous sprint retrospective session completed?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you re-poker in case of a requirement change in the middle of the sprint?	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Always 5/5
How often is your Product Owner part of the retrospective sessions and provide inputs?	Sometimes 1/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3
How often have you challenged requirements due to a feasibility issue?	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Never 0/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Always 10/10
Do you do automation testing for unit and system tests?	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3
Do you encounter situations when requirements are being reworked in the middle of sprint due to its incorrectness?	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Never 10/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Never 10/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10
Has your team velocity increased since the start of Sprint?	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3
How often you have a knowledge session with your team, on what you have built and get an opinion/feedback on the same?	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5
Are the defects/incidents discussed with all members within the team (in daily standup or another session)?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Always 5/5	Never 0/5
Do you have team activities for team building attended by all participants?	Sometimes 1/3	Never 0/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Sometimes 1/3
Do you proactively take responsibility for resolving any impediment?	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5
Do you prefer to be a Scrum master?	No 0/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	No 0/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3
Do you create technical documents during Sprint?	Never 0/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5

Timestamp	2019/12/20	2019/12/20	2019/12/20	2019/12/20	2019/12/20	2019/12/20	2019/12/20	2019/12/20
Team Scores	69 / 100	79 / 100	61 / 100	73 / 100	34 / 100	45 / 100	58 / 100	47 / 100
Survey Questions/Score	RESPONSES							
Does your colleague(s) need a reminder for daily standup?	No 3/3	No 3/3	Yes 0/3	No 3/3	Yes 0/3	No 3/3	No 3/3	No 3/3
Is your Product Backlog sorted by the Product Owner?	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Never 0/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3
Does your team gain mutual consent(after discussion) before finalizing the story points?	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5
How many times does your team manage to achieve a story point?	Sometimes 2/4	Always 4/4	Always 4/4	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Always 4/4	Sometimes 2/4
DEMO involving working product	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you encounter a story with a fixed timeline?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 5/5	Always 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
Have your team members changed(added/replaced) in the last 2 years within your team?	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	No 10/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10
How often are the action items of the previous sprint retrospective session completed?	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you re-poker in case of a requirement change in the middle of the sprint?	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5
How often is your Product Owner part of the retrospective sessions and provide inputs?	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Never 0/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3
How often have you challenged requirements due to a feasibility issue?	Sometimes 5/10	Always 10/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Never 0/10
Do you do automation testing for unit and system tests?	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3
Do you encounter situations when requirements are being reworked in the middle of sprint due to its incorrectness?	Sometimes 5/10	Never 10/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10
Has your team velocity increased since the start of Sprint?	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3
How often you have a knowledge session with your team, on what you have built and get an opinion/feedback on the same?	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
Are the defects/incidents discussed with all members within the team (in daily standup or another session)?	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you have team activities for team building attended by all participants?	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Sometimes 1/3	Never 0/3	Always 3/3	Never 0/3	Sometimes 1/3
Do you proactively take responsibility for resolving any impediment?	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5
Do you prefer to be a Scrum master?	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3
Do you create technical documents during Sprint?	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5

Timestamp	2019/12/20	2019/12/22	2019/12/23	2019/12/24	2019/12/25	2020/01/02	2020/01/06
Team Scores	57 / 100	45 / 100	54 / 100	49 / 100	48 / 100	46 / 100	43 / 100
Survey Questions/Score	RESPONSES						
Does your colleague(s) need a reminder for daily standup?	No 3/3	No 3/3	No 3/3	Yes 0/3	Yes 0/3	Yes 0/3	No 3/3
Is your Product Backlog sorted by the Product Owner?	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3
Does your team gain mutual consent(after discussion) before finalizing the story points?	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
How many times does your team manage to achieve a story point?	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Sometimes 2/4	Always 4/4
DEMO involving working product	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you encounter a story with a fixed timeline?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
Have your team members changed(added/replaced) in the last 2 years within your team?	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10	Yes 0/10
How often are the action items of the previous sprint retrospective session completed?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you re-poker in case of a requirement change in the middle of the sprint?	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5	Never 0/5
How often is your Product Owner part of the retrospective sessions and provide inputs?	Sometimes 1/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3
How often have you challenged requirements due to a feasibility issue?	Always 10/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10
Do you do automation testing for unit and system tests?	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	No 0/3	No 0/3
Do you encounter situations when requirements are being reworked in the middle of sprint due to its incorrectness?	Never 10/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10	Sometimes 5/10
Has your team velocity increased since the start of Sprint?	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3
How often you have a knowledge session with your team, on what you have built and get an opinion/feedback on the same?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5
Are the defects/incidents discussed with all members within the team (in daily standup or another session)?	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Always 5/5	Sometimes 2/5
Do you have team activities for team building attended by all participants?	Sometimes 1/3	Never 0/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3	Always 3/3	Sometimes 1/3
Do you proactively take responsibility for resolving any impediment?	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5	Yes 5/5
Do you prefer to be a Scrum master?	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3	Yes 3/3	Yes 3/3	No 0/3
Do you create technical documents during Sprint?	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Always 5/5	Never 0/5	Sometimes 2/5	Sometimes 2/5	Never 0/5

Distributed Agile Software Development Teams	
Co-located Software Development Teams with cultural diversity	
Co-located Software Development Teams without cultural diversity	

APPENDIX 3

F-Table ($\alpha = 0.05$)

/	df ₁ =1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
df ₂ =1	161.447	199.500	215.707	224.583	230.1619	233.9860	236.7684	238.8827	240.5433	241.8817
2	18.5128	19.0000	19.1643	19.2468	19.2964	19.3295	19.3532	19.3710	19.3848	19.3959
3	10.1280	9.5521	9.2766	9.1172	9.0135	8.9406	8.8867	8.8452	8.8123	8.7855
4	7.7086	6.9443	6.5914	6.3882	6.2561	6.1631	6.0942	6.0410	5.9988	5.9644
5	6.6079	5.7861	5.4095	5.1922	5.0503	4.9503	4.8759	4.8183	4.7725	4.7351
6	5.9874	5.1433	4.7571	4.5337	4.3874	4.2839	4.2067	4.1468	4.0990	4.0600
7	5.5914	4.7374	4.3468	4.1203	3.9715	3.8660	3.7870	3.7257	3.6767	3.6365
8	5.3177	4.4590	4.0662	3.8379	3.6875	3.5806	3.5005	3.4381	3.3881	3.3472
9	5.1174	4.2565	3.8625	3.6331	3.4817	3.3738	3.2927	3.2296	3.1789	3.1373
10	4.9646	4.1028	3.7083	3.4780	3.3258	3.2172	3.1355	3.0717	3.0204	2.9782
11	4.8443	3.9823	3.5874	3.3567	3.2039	3.0946	3.0123	2.9480	2.8962	2.8536

t-Table

Cumulative Probability (α)	t _{.50}	t _{.75}	t _{.80}	t _{.85}	t _{.90}	t _{.95}	t _{.975}	t _{.99}	t _{.995}	t _{.999}	t _{.9995}
one-tail	0.50	0.25	0.20	0.15	0.10	0.05	0.025	0.01	0.005	0.001	0.0005
two-tails	1.00	0.50	0.40	0.30	0.20	0.10	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.002	0.001
df=1	0.000	1.000	1.376	1.963	3.078	6.314	12.71	31.82	63.66	318.31	636.62
df=2	0.000	0.816	1.061	1.386	1.886	2.920	4.303	6.965	9.925	22.327	31.599
df=3	0.000	0.765	0.978	1.250	1.638	2.353	3.182	4.541	5.841	10.215	12.924
df=4	0.000	0.741	0.941	1.190	1.533	2.132	2.776	3.747	4.604	7.173	8.610
df=5	0.000	0.727	0.920	1.156	1.476	2.015	2.571	3.365	4.032	5.893	6.869
df=6	0.000	0.718	0.906	1.134	1.440	1.943	2.447	3.143	3.707	5.208	5.959
df=7	0.000	0.711	0.896	1.119	1.415	1.895	2.365	2.998	3.499	4.785	5.408
df=8	0.000	0.706	0.889	1.108	1.397	1.860	2.306	2.896	3.355	4.501	5.041
df=9	0.000	0.703	0.883	1.100	1.383	1.833	2.262	2.821	3.250	4.297	4.781
df=10	0.000	0.700	0.879	1.093	1.372	1.812	2.228	2.764	3.169	4.144	4.587
df=11	0.000	0.697	0.876	1.088	1.363	1.796	2.201	2.718	3.106	4.025	4.437
df=12	0.000	0.695	0.873	1.083	1.356	1.782	2.179	2.681	3.055	3.930	4.318
df=13	0.000	0.694	0.870	1.079	1.350	1.771	2.160	2.650	3.012	3.852	4.221
df=14	0.000	0.692	0.868	1.076	1.345	1.761	2.145	2.624	2.977	3.787	4.140
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df=z	0.000										
	0%	50%	60%	70%	80%	90%	95%	98%	99%	99.8%	99.9%
	Confidence Level										